

The Role of Islamic Sustainable Behaviour Toward Happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan

A thesis proffered in partial fulfilment of the prerequisites for the degree of Masters of Arts in Islamic Studies at International Open University (IOU) The Gambia

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Abstract

The depravity of youth behaviour that is happening today is very disturbing to society, and whatever happens to our youth today will undoubtedly make our future which will always depend on them. The expected behaviour at this time is very far from expectations where slander will always come depending on the youth shielding themselves in goodness. Happiness, which is one of the goals of the Muslim community, is indeed a challenge in achieving it where one of its prominent roles in schools that help shape the personality of today's youth in making sustainable behaviour in Islamic perspectives to shield themselves from the slander of the world.

Seeing the background that becomes a challenge for the development of sustainable Islamic behaviour, here we are moved to make research topics that can be researched from the development of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan in creating their personality in achieving happiness a goal rather than their obedience to Allah and His Messenger. The methodology used is mixed quantitative and qualitative with an emphasis on two variables in obtaining the results from the research.

Keywords: Islamic Behavior, Sustainability, Happiness, Muslim Community

Declarations

I, the undersigned, confirm that the work I presented as my thesis is my own work. Reference to the quotation from and discussion of any other person's creation has been correctly acknowledged within the position following the university guidelines for producing a thesis.

Kurniawan Arif Maspul

July 8th, 2022

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Success belongs to all of us, and of course, no one can give victory except with Allah's pleasure of Allah ﷻ, and I believe that success is always in the middle of the process until Allah ﷻ takes our lives. May Allah ﷻ honour those who glorify His *Deen*.

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CHAPTER ONE – INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of Study

Facing the current advanced era, it is very nice to see the young generation studying and developing and advancing their way of thinking and their outputs in their contribution to life and community (Morgan, 2007; Stiglitz, 2002; Usri et al., 2021). However, some of the challenges faced are, on the contrary, many young people today are detached from noble behaviour, especially the Muslim generation who live without the appropriate direction of Islamic behaviour (Hoque et al., 2013; Noble & McGrath, 2012; Ubale & Abdullah, 2015). Furthermore, many Muslims are intelligent but corrupt in behaviour, negatively impacting their bad behaviour on their attitudes and the people who interact with them. This bad behaviour results in a far-from happiness slump and always feels lacking and greedy (Ahmed, 2002; Dewi et al., 2021; Masyhuri et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, happiness is one of the outputs of one's behaviour in running life. Especially for Muslims, happiness is the general goal of human desire in producing interactive moral values between a servant and Allah ﷻ, a Muslim with his brother and a Muslim with the universe (Al-Seheel & Noor, 2016; Amalia et al., 2016; Bayat, 2013). All of them are related to the three bottom legs of sustainability, one of the foundations for Muslims, including Islamic sustainable behaviour. Islamic sustainable behaviour itself is not a new concept. The Qur'an and Sunnah have taught Muslims to behave sustainably in all aspects of life socially, economically and socially with the environment (Al-Jayyousi, 2016; Matali, 2012; Sarkawi et al., 2016). Moreover, morals or personal behaviour values have been embedded in the principles of a Muslim, which the Prophet ﷺ has left to *ummah* through the Qur'an and Sunnah. Muslim life is regulated in such a way as to have harmony in maintaining the pillars of Islamic sustainability, which has become a blessing for the universe (Hassan, 2016; Marsuki, 2009).

It is interesting to observe through students in the SMA Ibnu Umar Islamic School, one of the schools implementing Islamic values through a local teaching system, including instilling Islamic sustainable behaviour. The subjects taught and the cultivation of morals through Islamic studies are often held in schools weekly and monthly. One thing desired from the teaching is to make students understand the

purpose of life and make their daily lives meaningful and interact by instilling the Islamic sustainable behaviour values from their everyday behaviour, which produces happiness through Islamic sustainable behaviour (Al-Seheel & Noor, 2016; Raquib et al., 2020).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

With this concept in mind, the researcher shall carefully observe how far the Islamic sustainable behaviour values are instilled from their daily behaviour, using the title "The Role of Islamic Sustainable Behavior Toward Happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan". As the formulation of the problem which becomes the need for Islamic Sustainable Behavior to achieve the happiness of Ibnu Umar Islamic High School Students, South Tangerang, as follows:

- The implementation of Islamic education applied at SMA Islam Ibnu Umar, Tangerang Selatan, in its role in shaping sustainable Islamic behaviour to achieve student happiness
- Islamic morality from students to teachers
- Islamic morals from students to each other
- Islamic education has an effect on the formation of students' morals
- Efforts made by the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar to shape students' sustainable Islamic character
- Factors supporting, sustaining and hindering the implementation of Islamic education in the formation of students' Islamic character

Therefore, as to the uniqueness of Islamic teachings that teach and uphold Islamic personality and *akhlak al-karimah*, the researcher is interested in using the primary language of practice to understand the influence of Islamic sustainable behaviour; presented in the discussion. Through quantitative data analysis, the researcher will carry out the research results to understand more profoundly the impact of the Role of Islamic sustainable behaviour toward happiness among students in chapter IV of this thesis.

1.3 Significant of Research

The significance of the authors choosing the title "The Role of Islamic Sustainable Behavior on the Happiness of Islamic High School Students Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan" can be explained below:

1. Sustainability is a fundamental idea always discussed in the global community; here, Islamic behaviour becomes an attraction for the author to intensely discuss the concept and implications for Muslim youth.
2. In Tangerang Selatan, since modernisation has become a global topic, happiness is a behaviour that is currently most challenging to obtain among the local youth community. Here the author, as the developer of the youth counselling program for local youth, is one of the goals in acquiring these behaviours as a goal of Islamic behaviour.

1.4 Scope and Limitation

In the title, as stated above, the discussion will be devoted to the impact of Islamic Sustainable Behaviour Toward Happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan. In discussing happiness, the author focuses on the pleasant, the good life, and the meaningful life from the Islamic perspective. In the discussion about Islamic sustainable behaviour, the author will focus on data collection and analysis through Islamic behaviour and the sustainability of typical behaviour in Muslim youth (social, economic and environment).

Meanwhile, this research will have limitations and risks caused by the researcher or the respondent as the research object. The researcher will complete this research to produce a relevant report, such as what will be performed below, for limitation or solution steps to stem this risk. Those who are at stake in this research project include;

- 1) The writer's lack of more extensive knowledge in the fields of Islamic sustainable behaviour and happiness,
- 2) Limitations of the respondent in being open to providing information for completing this research.
- 3) The limitations of respondents in their knowledge of Islamic sustainable behaviour and happiness,
- 4) Limited costs in transportation and communication to complete the data taken from respondents.

The mitigation that can be carried out to solve this research includes;

- 1) Exploring the literature that will be discussed in the research
- 2) Seeking enlightenment through mentors and supervisors leads to finding complex terms to understand.

- 3) Communicate to the respondent well on the background to the purpose of this research.
- 4) Assisting respondents in opening up discussion spaces in Islamic sustainable behaviour and happiness.
- 5) Using all-digital space for communication and data retrieval is related to this research from respondents and whoever is relevant.

1.5 Research Questions

From the problem statement above, the researcher draws questions that will be studied through the following:

1. Is there any impact on the Islamic sustainable behaviour toward happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan?
2. How extensive is the impact of the Islamic sustainable behaviour toward happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan?
3. How significant is the contribution of Islamic sustainable behaviour to happiness for the people who interact with Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar, Tangerang Selatan?

1.6 Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to:

1. To find out the impact of Islamic sustainable behaviour on happiness for students at SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.
2. To find out how influential Islamic sustainable behaviour impacts students' happiness at SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.
3. To identify the enormous contribution of Islamic sustainable behaviour to happiness for people who interact with students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar, Tangerang Selatan.

1.7 Hypothesis

The hypotheses for this research have been formulated as follows:

1. Working hypothesis (H1)

The implication of Islamic sustainable behaviour has impacted the existence of happiness of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar students.

2. Null hypothesis (H0)

The implication of Islamic sustainable behaviour does not impact the happiness of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar students.

CHAPTER TWO – LITERATURE REVIEW

2. Literature Review

2.1 Happiness in Islam and General Perspective

In Arabic, the word happiness is *as-sa'adah*; which is found in Surah Hud verses 105-108:

يَوْمَ يَأْتُ لَا تَكَلِّمُ نَفْسٌ إِلَّا بِإِذْنِهِ فَمِنْهُمْ سُعِيُّبٌ وَسَعِيدٌ ﴿١٠٥﴾ فَأَمَّا الَّذِينَ شَفَعُوا فِي النَّارِ لَهُمْ فِيهَا زَفِيرٌ وَشَهِيقٌ ﴿١٠٦﴾ خَالِدِينَ فِيهَا مَا دَامَتِ السَّمٰوٰتُ وَالْاَرْضُ اِلَّا مَا شَاءَ رَبُّكَ اِنَّ رَبَّكَ فَعٰلٌ لِّمَا يُرِيْدُ ﴿١٠٧﴾ وَاَمَّا الَّذِينَ سُوْعِدُوْا فِى الْجَنَّةِ خٰلِدِيْنَ فِيْهَا مَا دَامَتِ السَّمٰوٰتُ وَالْاَرْضُ اِلَّا مَا شَاءَ رَبُّكَ عَطَاءٌ غَيْرٌ مَّجْدُوْدٌ ﴿١٠٨﴾

"When that Day arrives, no one will dare speak except with His permission. Some of them will be miserable, others joyful. As for those bound for misery, they will be in the fire, where they will be sighing and gasping, staying there forever, as long as the heavens and the earth will endure, except what your Lord wills. Surely your Lord does what He intends. And as for those destined to joy, they will be in Paradise, staying there forever, as long as the heavens and the earth will endure, except what your Lord wills—a generous giving, without end." (QS Hud: 105-108).

The hope of obtaining happiness is stated in the letter al-Baqarah, verse 201:

وَمِنْهُمْ مَّنْ يَقُوْلُ رَبَّنَا اِنَّا فِى الدُّنْيَا حَسَنَةٌ وَّفِى الْاٰخِرَةِ حَسَنَةٌ وَقِنَا عَذَابَ النَّارِ ﴿٢٠١﴾

Yet there are others who say, "Our Lord! Grant us the good of this world and the Hereafter, and protect us from the torment of the Fire." (QS Al-Baqarah: 201).

The virtues here are positive deeds that can bring people to inner peace. In the Qur'an, Allah ﷻ mentions that *aamanuu* is always associated with the word of *amilus shaalihah*. The word *aamanuu* is oriented toward the afterlife, whereas *amilus shaalihah* is introduced to the world. The term *aamanuu* refers to the happiness of the hereafter, while *amilus shaalihah* refers to worldly prosperity achieved by hard work and earnest effort (Heryanto, 2011).

Happiness is a term often used to describe a situation that has always been the goal of every human being, as a creature who wants to achieve its perfect existence (Sukardi, 2005: 83). happiness is a word translated from Arabic, *al-sa'adah*. To describe this in detail, experts have different views. And the authors of Arabic dictionaries have never provided a description of the meaning of the word *al-sa'adah* broadly. Most of them only explain that the word *al-sa'adah*, happiness, is the opposite of the word *al-sa'adah* is *saqowah*, suffering. The word *al-sa'adah* contains the meaning of good things. This meaning can be seen in the sentence *sa'adahullahu wa*

as'ada, meaning that Allah ﷻ gave him good things and made him in good condition. The word *al-sa'adah* in this sentence shows us that a person's happiness is a gift from Allah ﷻ alone. Thus the meaning of the word *al-sa'adah* is etymologically identical to the word *al-sa'd* (Noddings, 2003; Nasr, 2014)

Some other authors state that *al-sa'adah* means Allah ﷻ's help given to humans so that they can do good and avoid doing evil. In this sense, *al-sa'adah* is synonymous with the word *al-tawfiq*; welfare refers to understanding help as *sa'adahullahu musa'adatan wa sa'dan*, which means to help. And in the end, writers and writers in modern times conclude that if *al-sa'adah* is taken from the root words *sa'ada*, *yas'adu*, *sa'adatan*, the word *al-sa'adah* has the meaning of a reflection of a good and stable soul. If taken from the root words *sa'ada*, *yas'adu*, *sa'dan*, *al-sa'adah*, then *al-sa'adah* has the sense (of) feeling prosperous and calm in one's soul (Nasr, 2014; Abde & Salih, 2015).

In Al-Farabi's observation, as written in his book, *al-Tanbih 'ala Sabil al-Sa'adah*, ordinary people generally interpret *al-sa'adah* or happiness, as a form of life (state) that is without problems and difficulties. , both material tests (possessions), work, a place to live and always live in harmony with family and friends. In other words, *al-sa'adah*, happiness in this sense, reflects well-being in this world. The description of *al-sa'adah* above, according to Al-Farabi is no different from *al-ladzdzah*, enjoyment, because these two terms have essential elements such as taste in common. Satisfied, willing to enjoy, not afflicted by disaster, or if it is very light and does not affect anything in his life. In Aristotle's view, *al-ladzdzah*, enjoyment, is essential for humans to get *al-sa'adah*, happiness; but it is not the only condition. Thus, *al-ladzdzah* is not the same *al-sa'adah*. Epicurus states that if *al-ladzdzah* can last and does not change, it can also be called *al-sa'adah*, happiness (Jabbali, 2018; Hamidi et al., 2010; Cooper, 1987).

Islam's view of individuals rests on efforts not to be disappointed with anything received from Allah ﷻ. According to *Shari'*, a little or a lot is still grateful and accepted as the best pliers. On the other hand, the *qana'ah* itself consists of five aspects that are directly related to an individual's life, including:

- Accept willingly what Allah ﷻ has given
- Ask Allah ﷻ for a worthy addition and keep trying

- Accept the provisions of Allah ﷻ patiently
- Put your trust in Allah ﷻ
- Not interested in the tricks and pleasures of the world.

The five aspects above practically lead a person to happiness. With a *qana'ah* attitude, a person will not be dazzled by the achievements of others but is busy managing and taking care of what he has received. The meaning of happiness for people who believe can judge and decorate this life according to the value and portion that should be. Al-Ghazali once said true happiness and delicacy are when one can remember Allah ﷻ. With the remembrance of Allah ﷻ, the heart feels at peace and calm (Haque, 2004).

Happiness is the fruit of actions in the world that are immediately felt. But happiness is also enjoyed in the hereafter; heaven, whose enjoyment is never interrupted. As explained in verse above. In several hadiths, the Prophet ﷺ. Informing us that every human being has his fate recorded, whether happy or miserable since he was still in the form of a fetus in his mother's stomach. He also explained that true happiness is happiness in faith and piety. The following is a hadith of the Prophet Muhammad ﷺ about happiness;

حَدَّثَنَا بُنْدَارٌ، قَالَ حَدَّثَنَا عَبْدُ الرَّحْمَنِ بْنُ مَهْدِيٍّ، قَالَ حَدَّثَنَا شُعْبَةُ، عَنْ عَاصِمِ بْنِ عُبَيْدِ اللَّهِ، قَالَ سَمِعْتُ سَالِمَ بْنَ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ، يُحَدِّثُ عَنْ أَبِيهِ، قَالَ قَالَ عُمَرُ يَا رَسُولَ اللَّهِ أَرَأَيْتَ مَا تَعْمَلُ فِيهِ أَمْرٌ مُبْتَدَأٌ أَوْ فِيمَا قَدْ فُرِعَ مِنْهُ فَقَالَ " فِيمَا قَدْ فُرِعَ مِنْهُ يَا ابْنَ الْخَطَّابِ وَكُلُّ مَيْسَرٍ أَمَّا مَنْ كَانَ مِنْ أَهْلِ السَّعَادَةِ فَإِنَّهُ يَعْمَلُ لِلْسَّعَادَةِ وَأَمَّا مَنْ كَانَ مِنْ أَهْلِ الشَّقَاءِ فَإِنَّهُ يَعْمَلُ لِلشَّقَاءِ " . قَالَ أَبُو عِيسَى وَفِي الْبَابِ عَنْ عَلِيِّ وَحَدِيثَ بْنِ أَبِي سَيْدٍ وَأَنْسِ وَعِمْرَانَ بْنِ حُصَيْنٍ . وَهَذَا حَدِيثٌ حَسَنٌ صَحِيحٌ .

'Asim bin 'Ubaidullah said, "I heard Salim bin 'Abdullah narrating a Hadith from his father who said: "Umar said: "O Messenger of Allah! Do you see that what we do is a new matter- or a matter initiated – or it is a matter already concluded?" He ﷺ said: "O Ibn Al-Khattab! It is a matter already concluded. For everyone is suited (for that for which he is created). As for one who is among the people of happiness, then he works for happiness, and as for the one who is among the people of misery, then he works for his misery." (Jami' at-Tirmidhi 2135 - Hadith Hasan)

Moreover From Saad ibn Abi Waqqash, Rasulullah ﷺ said:

سَعَادَةُ لَابِنِ آدَمَ ثَلَاثٌ ، وَشَقَاوَةٌ لَابِنِ آدَمَ ثَلَاثٌ فَمَنْ سَعَادَةٌ ابْنِ آدَمَ : الزَّوْجَةُ الصَّالِحَةُ ، وَالْمَرْكَبُ الصَّالِحُ ، وَالْمَسْكَنُ الْوَاسِعُ ، وَشَقَاوَةٌ لَابِنِ آدَمَ ثَلَاثٌ : الْمَسْكَنُ السَّوْءُ ، وَالْمَرْأَةُ السَّوْءُ ، وَالْمَرْكَبُ السَّوْءُ

"There are three things that make the son of Adam happy, and misfortune for the son of Adam are three. From the happiness of the son of Adam: a good wife, a good vehicle, and a spacious home, and misery for the son of Adam are three: a bad home, a bad woman, and a bad vehicle." (Shahih al-Jami' 3629)

Happiness is the pleasure and tranquillity of life (both physically and mentally), which includes luck and luck that are physically and mentally. Happiness is pleasure, peace, and calm. So, happiness can be interpreted as feelings of joy, peace, quiet, and luck felt by individuals. Happiness is a term that describes and represents positive feelings; it is when a person feels more pleasant events than actually happened and forgets more about destructive events. In his book *Authentic Happiness*, happiness results from self-assessment and life, which contains positive emotions, such as overflowing comfort and joy, and positive activities that do not fulfil any emotional components, such as absorption and engagement. Individuals who get authentic happiness (genuine) have identified and cultivated or trained the essential strengths (consisting of strengths and virtues) and use them in everyday life, both in work, love, play and parenting (Seligman, 2002; Haron et al., 2020).

Theory of happiness in two views; hedonic and eudaimonic perspectives. The hedonic statement states that happiness is only obtained when choices and enjoyment exist for the mind and body. This view says that happiness is subjective. This is also expressed that hedonic happiness comes from pleasures outside the individual. For example, we can feel happiness in terms of material amusements and try to get more enjoyment from ourselves to achieve happiness. While the eudaimonic view has different meanings regarding the existence of happiness, the eudaimonic idea states that happiness is more objective and subjective pleasure cannot be included with happiness. Eudaimonic happiness gratification. The nature of eudaimonic happiness arises from within the individual and is not affected by the individual's external conditions. Eudaemonic happiness will only be obtained through activities aligned with the heart's true purpose (Ryan & Deci, 2001; Seligman, 2002).

Happiness comes from the word happy. The meaning of the word content is different from the word happy. Philosophically, the word happy can be interpreted as complete spiritual comfort and enjoyment, a sense of satisfaction, and the absence of imperfections in mind to feel calm and peaceful. This happiness is abstract and cannot be touched or handled; it is closely linked to the person's psyche. So true happiness can

be obtained from improving the quality of oneself, not from comparing oneself with others (Huta & Ryan, 2010; Seligman, 2002).

Happiness is a positive attitude towards life, a form of possession of cognitive and affective components. The mental aspect of happiness consists of a positive evaluation of life, which is measured either by standards or expectations terms of; affective happiness consists of what we commonly call a sense of well-being, discovering the richness of life or being profitable or feeling satisfied or fulfilled by good things (Nawjin et al., 2010).

Two things must be fulfilled to achieve happiness: affection and life satisfaction. Life satisfaction is a tangible form of happiness where happiness is something more than an achievement of goals because, in reality, happiness is always associated with better health, higher creativity and a better workplace. There are four signs of people who have happiness in their lives: people who respect themselves, are confident, open, and can control themselves. Honest people, optimistic, have high self-esteem and have good self-control. Happiness comes from pleasure and the ending of suffering (Cohn et al., 2009; Hoag, 1986).

Moreover, it can be concluded that happiness is a positive feeling that can create a pleasant experience in the form of feelings of pleasure and peace and includes peace of mind, life satisfaction and the absence of feelings of stress or suffering. These conditions are conditions the content of the happiness felt by the individual. The concept of Happiness in Islam is not a stand-alone one, but it is closely related to the notion of monotheism (*at-tauhid*). Happiness is a feeling that liberates humans from worshipping anyone but Allah ﷻ. Total surrender to Allah ﷻ is the most essential part of happiness itself. In essence, humans are nothing, nothing and have nothing. Everything that exists is only a loan from Him ﷻ (Tiliouine, 2014).

In Islam, the existence of an apostle cannot be ignored. Apostles are messengers (treatises). The last messenger is Muhammad ﷺ, without whom individuals will not encounter the teachings of Islam as individuals study and practice in everyday life. If gratitude is not only seen as an obligation but also an expression of love and affection, then pray and greet the Prophet Muhammad ﷺ. The most human face of happiness is when the individual can thank the Creator and His Messenger ﷺ. Islam states that

"welfare" and "happiness" do not refer to humans' physical and physical nature. Prosperity and happiness refer to self-confidence in the ultimate, absolute essence that is sought: belief in the rights of Allah ﷻ and reaping the deeds that are carried out by oneself based on that belief and obeying one's heart. Faith in Allah ﷻ is fundamental because human existence is not by itself but created by Allah ﷻ. So, happiness is the condition of the individual's heart filled with belief (faith) and behaves according to that belief (Tiliouine, 2014; Heryanto, 2011).

According to al-Ghazali, the peak of happiness in humans is if the individual succeeds in achieving essential *tauhid* and has known Allah. Furthermore, al-Ghazali stated: "Know that everything is happy if we feel the pleasure, pleasure and deliciousness then the taste is according to each other's feelings. So the delicacy (eyes) is seeing a beautiful appearance, the pleasure of the ear hearing a melodious voice, as well as all other members and the human body". Many verses of the Qur'an command humans to pay attention and think about the phenomena of the universe. That includes thinking about themselves. In addition to the *Kauniyah* verses, Allah also sent down the *qauliyah* verses in verbal revelation to His last messenger, the Prophet Muhammad ﷺ. Therefore, in QS Ali Imran 18-19, it is stated that those who have knowledge are those who testify and attest that "There is no god but Allah" and testify that "Indeed there is *Deen* in the view of Allah is Islam." (Yahya et al., 2020; Al-Ghazzali et al., 2015).

Individual believes the goal of a perfect life of happiness is not in this world but in the hereafter. True happiness is that which is linked between this world and the afterlife. This criterion should be the leading indicator of successful educational program. The success of education in Islam is not measured by how expensive school fees are, how much is accepted at State Universities, etc. But whether schooling can give birth to civilised humans who know their God and worship their Creator. Knowledgeable humans like this live happily in faith and belief whose lives are not swayed by circumstances. In any condition, the individual's life will be happy because he knows Allah ﷻ, is pleased with His decisions and tries to harmonise his life with Allah ﷻ' s regulations revealed through His messenger ﷺ (Hamidi et al., 2010; El-Ghazali & Series, 1994).

In the view of Islam, happiness in life does not dwell on the material side. Although Islam recognises that material is part of the element of joy. Islam basically views material problems as a means, not an end. Therefore, Islam pays excellent attention to *ma'nawi* factors, such as having noble behaviour as a way to get happiness in life (Badhwar, 2014). The happiness in the world – Islam has established several laws and criteria that direct humans to achieve satisfaction in life. It's just that Islam emphasises that the life of this world is nothing but a way to the hereafter. While the real-life that individuals must strive for in the afterlife.

Hereafter happiness – The happiness of the hereafter is eternal. Be a reward for the piety of servants while living in the world. Islam has set the task of humans on earth as caliphs in it. In charge of prospering the land and realising the needs of humans there. In its implementation, there are always difficulties, so it requires individuals to be serious and patient. Life is not only the convenience desired and dreamed of by each individual. In fact, it constantly changes from easy to difficult, from healthy to sick, from poor to rich, or vice versa. Life in heaven is eternal in nature; the happiness one obtains is an endless continuation, joy without sorrow, knowledge without ignorance, and the sufficiency of nothing is needed to achieve perfect satisfaction (Abde & Saleh, 2015; Joshanloo, 2013).

Meanwhile, the following methods are ways to achieve happiness: 1. Have faith and do good deeds 2. Have noble behaviour that encourages doing good to others 3. Increase *dhikr* and feel always accompanied by Allah ﷻ 4. Maintain health (Haque, 2004). Health here covers all sides; body, soul, mind and spirit. Maintaining a healthy body is human nature because it is related to survival and a means to meet material needs such as eating, drinking, clothing, and vehicles. Mental health; many individuals ignore mental health and do not care about how to maintain it, even though it is a mental health problem pillar to achieving happiness. Mental health is established with faith, decorated with commendable morals, and sterilised from bad morals such as anger, pride, miserliness, greed, envy, and other bad morals (Alavi, 2008; Metcalf, 1984). Therefore, Islam pays excellent attention to the soul's education and purifies it with noble qualities.

Regarding spiritual health, the health of the mind is the main reason humans receive *taklif* (the burden of the *Shari'ah*). The leading cause that eliminates the

awareness of sense is things that are intoxicating and forbidden. Therefore Allah ﷻ ordered to guard it and forbid anything that harms and destroys it. Shari'ah is very concerned about the means that can maintain spiritual health. So that a *mu'min* is instructed to do *dhikrullah* at all times as required; to fulfil spiritual nutrition such as the commandment of obligatory prayer, fasting, zakat, pilgrimage and a broader form in the form of sunnah deeds and all deeds to get closer to Allah ﷻ. These acts of worship bind a servant with his Lord and return the individual to the Creator when he is busy with the world (Ramli et al., 2014; Al-'Allāf, 2003).

2.2 Happiness and its Aspects

There are three aspects are a source of happiness for each individual according to Seligman (2002), namely:

- a. Positive relationships are created when individuals get the support of others to develop self-esteem, solve problems and are physically healthy individuals.
- b. Full involvement means participating in various activities with the family. By being fully involved, not only physically active but the heart and mind also participate in these activities.
- c. Finding meaning in everyday life – The discovery of importance in daily life in question is how individuals think positively when carrying out daily activities by being fully involved in their actions to create a sense of happiness in the individual.

According to Shaver and Freedman (Fordyce, 1977), there are three essences of happiness which are called the "three A's of happiness", namely as follows:

- a. Acceptance – Shaver and Freedman say that happiness is how individuals view their own situation and not compare with other people's. Happiness depends on accepting and enjoying other people's circumstances and what they have and maintaining a balance between hope and achievement.
- b. Affection – Love is a normal thing experienced by humans. Compassion arises from the attitude of acceptance of others towards oneself. The more well-received by others, the more affection is expected. The more love that is felt, the more happiness the individual experiences.
- c. Performance – Achievement is the achievement of an individual goal. Happiness will be created along with the achievements the person has achieved.

If individuals have unrealistic goals, it will lead to failure, resulting in feelings of dissatisfaction and dissatisfaction.

The same thing is also explained by Diener et al. (1985), who group the components of aspects of happiness as follows:

- a. The affective aspect is divided into positive affect and negative affect. Positive affect and negative affect are emotional experiences in the form of positive and negative emotions. This affective aspect is the emotional experience of joy, excitement, satisfaction, and other emotions.
- b. The cognitive component comes from the satisfaction individuals feel concerning themselves, their family, peers, health, finances, work, and leisure time.

Based on some of the descriptions above, it can be concluded that there are two aspects of happiness; affective aspects and cognitive aspects. The affective element is satisfaction from emotional experiences due to acceptance, affection, and achievement. Affective aspects include positive affect and negative affect; emotional experiences in the form of positive and negative emotions. While the cognitive aspects are satisfaction that comes from an attitude of acceptance, affection and achievements obtained from various areas of life such as self, family, peers, health, finances, achievements achieved, and the amount of free time that can be enjoyed (Clark, 2015; Andrews & Robinson, 1991).

2.3 Factors Affecting Happiness

According to Seligman (2002), two factors affect individual happiness, but not all of them have a significant influence. The following is a description of the external and internal factors that contribute to happiness;

a. Internal factors

Internal factors can arise from several personal things, whereas Seligman (2002) advances something that can affect happiness.

- 1) Behaviour Strength – Seligman (2002) states that individuals who have the strength of behaviour and apply it in all areas of life that are lived, then the individual will feel satisfied and have a happy life. It divides positive human feelings into 24 behaviour strengths under 6 virtues (virtues). Respecting and appreciating others, job satisfaction, material sufficiency, and healthy

communities and families. Behaviour strengths are good characteristics that lead individuals to achieve integrity or positive traits reflected in thoughts, feelings and behaviour. In addition, behaviour strength will provide tangible outcomes such as happiness, self-acceptance (both self and others), instructions for living life, competence, mastery, physical and mental health, prosperity and supportive social networks,

- 2) Satisfaction with the past – Satisfaction with the past can be achieved in three ways: letting go of the past as a determinant of the individual's future, being grateful for the good things in life will increase positive memories and forgiving and forgetting one's past feelings.
- 3) Optimism about the future
- 4) Happiness in the present – Happiness today involves two things: Pleasure and Gratification. Pleasure is the pleasure that has sensory solid, and emotional components are temporary and involve little thought. Gratification is an activity that is very liked by individuals but does not always involve certain feelings, and the duration is longer than pleasure. Activities that give rise to gratification generally have challenges, growing skills, concentration and purpose.

b. External Factors

Likewise, external factors can arise from several things outside of personal, whereas here Seligman (2002) suggests something that can affect happiness.

- 1) Money – A person's financial condition affects his satisfaction and happiness. However, it is not always for individuals with a lot of income, and their income continues to increase, accompanied by increased happiness.
- 2) Wedding – Marriage has more influence on happiness than money. The United States Center for National Opinion Research surveyed 35,000 Americans over the past 30 years; 40% of married people said they were delighted, while 24% of not-married people who divorced, separated, and their partner died also said they were happy. Because not all marriages are also always able to increase happiness. A marriage that is not harmonious can actually reduce enjoyment. On the other hand, harmonious marriages increase people's happiness in general.
- 3) Social Life – Seligman (2005) found that all people in the happiest 10% of people are currently involved in a romantic relationship. Pleased people tend to spend time interacting and socialising rather than alone.

- 4) Health – Health that can affect happiness is subjective. The individual's subjective perception of how healthy he is is crucial concerning joy.
- 5) Religion – The causal relationship between religion and a healthier and more pro-society life has become widely known; any beliefs prohibit drug use, crime and infidelity. On the other hand, it encourages charity, simple life and hard work.
- 6) Age – A study of the happiness of 60,000 adults in 40 countries divided pleasure into three components: life satisfaction, pleasant affect and unpleasant affect. Life satisfaction increases slowly with age, the nice effect decreases slightly, and the undesirable impact does not change.
- 7) Education, Climate, Race and Gender – These four things have not extensive enough influence on the level of individual happiness. Education can improve slightly in low-income individuals because education is a means to achieve a better income. The climate in the area where the person lives and race also have little influence on happiness. While gender, there is no significant difference between men and women in their emotional states, but this is because women tend to be happier and sadder than men.

Meanwhile, according to Taylor & Brown (1988), the factors that influence happiness in individuals are as follows:

a. Internal factors

- 1) Genetics – Genetics can affect happiness in individuals. This genetic factor can be seen in how individuals perceive happiness.
- 2) Optimism – Optimism possessed by individuals will lead to happiness. This is because optimism will make individuals always positive.

b. External Factors

- 1) Culture – Cultures with social similarities have higher levels of happiness. This increased happiness is also found in societies with individualist cultures rather than collective cultures.
- 2) Relationship – Relationships here include marital relations, family relationships, and close friends. A good relationship is characterised by good communication.
- 3) Environment – The geographical location of a person's residence dramatically affects the strength of a person's positive feelings. Good weather affects a

person's upbeat mood and vice versa. In addition, sounds of nature can add to a person's positive emotions and even reduce the aggressiveness of people who hear them (Alvarsson et al., 2010).

- 4) Physical aspect – Maintaining health is also essential to pay attention to since there will be psychological turmoil when suffering from a specific disease. The physical element here is more about the health that exists in the individual; personal mental health/fitness leads to happiness.
- 5) Productivity – Learning, education, results achieved, achievements and work are forms of productivity that lead to positive feelings and happiness.

According to the two figures above, the factors that influence happiness are: It is influenced by environmental factors where the individual lives or works, interactions with friends, family and life partners, and personal health factors. Internal factors also affect individual happiness, such as the strength of sustainable behaviour, satisfaction with the past, optimism about the future, and happiness with the present.

2.4 Individual Behaviours

Happiness in every individual can get the same enjoyment, but not everyone can have satisfaction. According to Myers (2012), a psychiatrist who has successfully conducted research on solutions to find happiness for modern humans. Four characteristics always exist in individuals who have joy in their lives, namely:

- a. Appreciate yourself – In general, happy individuals have high enough confidence to solve their problems.
- b. Optimistic – Optimistic individuals believe those extraordinary events have permanent causes and bad events are temporary, so they try to be harder at every opportunity so that the individual can experience good events.
- c. Open – Happy individuals are generally more open to others and are more likely to help others who need their help.
- d. Able to control selfness – Happy individuals generally have control over their lives. Individuals feel they have strengths or advantages and usually do better in school or work.

Based on the characterisation above, it can be concluded that individuals who have characteristics such as individual who have happiness will respect themselves more, are more optimistic, more open and able to control themselves.

2.5 Happiness in Adolescence

If adolescents successfully overcome their problems and have confidence in their ability to solve problems without the help of adults, the period of unhappiness will gradually decrease. When teenagers are in the last grade of high school, and their views and actions will be as adults, feelings of happiness will gradually replace unhappiness. This will cause teenagers to appreciate the decisions they have made. A happy teenager is a teenager who can be realistic about his abilities and set goals according to what is achieved. Teenagers will continue to try and direct their efforts to achieve their goals. Adolescents also increase self-confidence based on knowledge of past successes against previously disturbing feelings of inadequacy (Hurlock, 1980).

The part of self from the individual teenager. Adolescents also have control in which they are regulated by the environment and themselves. The role of this environment is held by parents and friends. If the power of the environment and oneself is reasonable, it will make adolescents satisfied with their needs. Happy adolescents will have good self-acceptance, overcome the problems they face, be realistic about their ability to achieve goals, and get love from their families. Meanwhile, unhappy adolescents will have poor self-adjustment, such as being unrealistic, their achievements do not meet expectations, so they are dissatisfied with themselves and reject themselves (Hurlock, 1980).

Based on the characterisation above, it can be concluded that happy adolescents will have more confidence in their own abilities to solve existing problems, optimism about achieving their goals, and good self-control. However, unhappy teens will have poor adjustments.

2.6 Strength of Sustainable Behaviour

1. Understanding Behaviour

Strength of Behaviour or character strengths consists of two words; strength and character. The person's behaviour can be interpreted as individuals with a specific personality or traits used as personal strengths; the word behaviour is defined as character or nature. Behaviour is a quality or characteristic that remains continuous and eternal that can be used as a feature to identify an individual, an object or an event. Behaviour is synonymous with the attribute (characteristics or distinctive traits) or the integration of individual traits in the form of a unit or similarity (Peterson & Park, 2012; McGrath, 2015). Behaviour as personality evaluated and

personality as behaviour devaluated. It is a set of codes of behaviour displayed when an individual or his behaviour is owned by someone else. For this reason, the classification of good and evil is always used in assessing a person's behaviour. In other words, sustainable behaviour is an evaluated personality (Sen, 1973).

One of the Islamic leaders also argues about behaviour; According to Al Ghazali, behaviour is morality. A moral is a tool used to optimise potential data sources to achieve the welfare of human life in the world and hereafter. Therefore, how do humans use the possible available resources to improve lives for the better? So that this character or behaviour is a trait embedded in the human soul, from which comes actions that are easy to do without considering reason. Sustainable behaviour is a positive trait consisting of an enormous behaviour (virtue) raised by individuals to deal with a situation or environmental condition (situational themes). Good behaviour is the quality of the individual that makes the individual continue to be seen as morally good. Positive behaviour can be seen in feelings, thoughts and individual behaviour (Hasan & Tamam, 2018; Michalos, 1980).

Virtue is the primary behaviour; individuals universally own human goodness. Virtue is universal because virtue is a good characteristic in humans and is used to complete their tasks and problems. But in the process of life's journey, virtue may change. Concerning socio-cultural, virtue is universal and exists in every culture. Still, each culture will interpret virtue from a different perspective so that the virtues that appear to be owned by individuals in certain cultures will be other. Based on historical records, virtue has existed and been studied for a long time concerning the six virtues: wisdom and knowledge, courage, humanity, justice, temperance, and transcendence. Virtue is built and displayed by twenty-four sustainable behaviour strengths through thoughts, feelings and individual behaviour. The strength of the behaviour portrayed by the individual is also influenced by the situational themes they face, so that the individual's thoughts, feelings and behaviours may differ in each situational composition (Dahlsgaard et al., 2005; Peterson & Seligman, 2004).

Situational themes are situations that encourage someone to display behaviour strengths in a certain way so that the same sustainable behaviour strengths can be shown differently. Virtue, sustainable behaviour strength and situational themes are

three hierarchical classification concepts ranging from abstract to concrete and general to specific (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). Based on the characterisation above, it can be concluded that sustainable behaviour strength is the strength possessed by each unique individual, and good behaviours will appear in certain situations.

2. Behaviour Strength Classification

Meanwhile, there are six virtues consisting of twenty-four behaviour strengths (Peterson & Seligman, 2004):

a. Wisdom and Knowledge

Understood as cognitive ability for skill and knowledge that is the foundation of achieving a good life. Five behaviour strengths display wisdom and understanding, namely:

- 1) Creativity – Creativity is shown in the form of the ability to generate new ideas and behaviours that are recognised for their authenticity and are adaptive.
- 2) Curiosity – Curiosity is understood as inquisitiveness and an individual's intrinsic desire for experience and knowledge.
- 3) Openness – Mind Open-mindedness is to think about something thoroughly and see from various sides or consider the existing evidence
- 4) Love of Learning – The strength of sustainable behaviour is possessed by individuals by liking activities related to the search for new knowledge, general skills, and the desire to develop an interest in many things.
- 5) Perspective – Perspective is the most mature and closest force to wisdom itself; perspective allows individuals to glimpse the world as a whole to understand themselves and others.

b. Determination

Virtue perseverance is the second virtue that is understood as the emotional ability to achieve goals, even at the beginning of external and internal demands. Four behaviour strengths display the integrity of determination:

- 1) Courage – Shelp defines courage as an effort to obtain or maintain things that are considered suitable for oneself and others. Courage appears when individuals are in threatening, dangerous and risky situations.
- 2) Perseverance – Perseverance is a continuous action taken to achieve a goal despite obstacles, difficulties, or discouragement.
- 3) Honesty – Honesty describes the individual's behaviour to act rightly for himself and others, following the goals and commitments.
- 4) Vitality – Behaviour is shown with passion and passion in living life, doing things with all their heart and seeing life as an adventure.

c. Humanity and Love

Humanity is the third virtue that is a positive trait in maintaining interpersonal relationships. Humanity is the ability to love and do good to adapt to the environment. Initially built through interpersonal relationships, which later expanded to social relationships. Three character strengths describe humanity and love:

- 1) Love – Love is a person's cognitive, conative and affective condition. It is understood as caring for oneself and others by accepting one's strengths and weaknesses.
- 2) Kindness – Kindness is a voluntary act of giving help and caring for others. Empathy and sympathy are essential components of kindness.
- 3) Social Intelligence – Social intelligence is the ability to recognise and influence oneself and others to adapt well to their environment.

d. Justice

Justice is the fourth virtue defined as the ability to pay attention to the rights and obligations of individuals in community life. Three behaviour strengths describe justice, namely:

- 1) Membership in Group – Membership in groups focuses on social bonds as citizens, namely the ability to sacrifice one's own interests to prioritise the group's welfare.
- 2) Justice and Equality – Fairness and equality are the ability to treat everyone fairly and provide equal opportunities to all groups.

- 3) Leadership – Leadership refers to treating, influencing, directing, and motivating other people or groups to achieve success.

e. Simplicity

The fifth virtue is related to the ability to restrain oneself and not do something considered excessive. This virtue consists of four properties, namely:

- 1) Forgive – Forgiveness represents a series of prosocial changes in individuals who experience damaged relationships with others.
- 2) Humility – This simplicity means simple, quiet, letting the results of their efforts do the talking, not looking for popularity.
- 4) Carefulness – Prudence is a strength of character in self-management that helps individuals achieve their long-term goals. Individuals will be careful in choosing and not concerned with momentary pleasures.
- 5) Self Regulation – Self-regulation is how individuals use the ability to regulate their self-responses to achieve goals and meet social standards (Seligman, 2005).

f. Transcendence

Transcendence is the last behaviour strength proposed by Peterson and Seligman (2004); this behaviour strength is related to establishing a relationship with a more significant universal force and interpreting the individual's life. Five character strengths describe transcendence, namely:

- 1) Beauty Appreciation – Appreciation of beauty is the ability to discover, recognise and take pleasure in the physical environment and the social world
- 2) Gratitude – Gratitude is gratitude in response to a gift. Individuals who are grateful for everything that happens in their lives will always take the time to express gratitude.
- 3) Optimism – Optimism is related to how individuals view their future. Individuals think about the future, expect the best results in the future and feel confident about the results.
- 4) Humour – Humour may be easier to recognise than define, but among its current meanings are a) the playful recognition, pleasure or creating oddities, b) being seen as cheerful and able to see the good in times of

adversity by maintaining a good mood, c) being able to make other people smile or laugh.

- 6) Religiosity – Religiosity refers to the belief and practice that there is a transcendent (nonphysical) dimension to life.
- 7) Spirit – Enthusiasm refers to the individual going through his day. The feeling when running every activity. In addition, individuals have a sense of being inspired by something.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that six virtues include twenty-four character strengths, namely wisdom and knowledge (creativity, curiosity, open-mindedness, love of learning, perspective), determination (courage, perseverance, honesty, vitality), and humanity. And love (love, kindness, social intelligence), justice (group membership, justice and equality and leadership), temperance (forgiveness, humility, prudence, self-regulation), transcendence (appreciation of beauty, gratitude, optimism, humour, religiosity, passion).

3. Strength of Behaviour in Youth

According to Seligman (2005), behaviour strength is owned by all individuals. Each individual must face certain situations that make the individual show the behaviour to survive. Certain situations can also be called situational themes. Many character strengths exist, but individuals can only use a few behaviour strengths when faced with certain conditions, so not all character strengths appear simultaneously. For illustration, when an individual is encountered with a difficult position regarding finances, the individual will try to meet the problematic situation with perseverance. Perseverance is one of the strengths of behaviour based on the virtue of determination (Peterson and Seligman, 2004).

The strength of sustainable behaviour in individuals can be seen based on the developmental tasks undertaken. One of them is in adolescence. In adolescence, six- behaviour powers stand out the most. These six character strengths are in different virtues. The most prominent behaviour in adolescents is curiosity, perseverance, love, group membership, prudence, and optimism. This is in line with developments in adolescence, where adolescence is a period of beginning to open up to many things, build relationships, and start thinking about the future (Peterson & Seligman, 2004).

2.7 Sustainability and Islamic Behaviour

The idea and concept of sustainability are based on three main elements: constant economic growth, protection and preservation of the environment, and respect and improvement of social and human rights. All three interrelated factors must be simultaneously sustainable since they can only shape a just, liveable, and sustainable world. Such an approach to development is called the integral or holistic approach. The intersections of the circle, i.e. the pillars of economic growth, represent social-ecological, socio-economic and ecological financial elements (Ivković et al., 2014). The article also stated that sustainability is often a long-term goal (i.e. a more sustainable world).

In contrast, sustainability refers to the many processes and pathways to achieve it (Robèrt et al., 2002). As its element of typical human behaviour, it is also described in the Handbook of Research on Pedagogical Innovations for Sustainable Development, sustainable behaviour that is meant "is behaviour that implies people's values, norms, beliefs, senses of responsibility in deliberate actions focused on providing well-being of all living beings, including present and future generations." (Thomas, 2014)

Meanwhile, moderation (*wasatiyyah*) is a central tenet of Islam and a way of life with a clear affirmation in the Quran. The Qur'an conveys that Allah is the One and only, and the creation of this ummah as a middle way community (*ummatan wasatan*) for modesty, therefore as a guide and guide for their life on earth (al-Baqarah, 2: 143). Moderation doesn't just talk about individual personal behaviour and the collective ethos of communities, but also about using the earth's resources and overseeing its natural environment. The significance of this teaching is elsewhere sustained in the Qur'an, where the Quran states of a balance (*al-mizan*) in the creation of the earth and the terrestrial universe. It's been created in a form and through an outstanding balance of nature, "so consider everything justly and without disturbing the balance (which Allah ﷻ has decreed)" (QS al-Rahman, 55:7).

Three other concepts relevant to sustainability are conveyed in the Qur'an, first, the task of humans as caliphs (leaders) on earth to carry out the mission and responsibility to uphold a just socio-economic order in it (QS al-Baqarah, 2:30). Followed by utilising the earth's natural resources such as land, water, air, fire, forests, oceans and other energies considered rights and common property of the people. Since human beings are the vicegerents of Allah ﷻ on earth, they must be able to take every

forethought to secure the rights and interests of other inhabitants with the concept of balance, which includes animals and birds whose needs are also met, not only for the recent generation but also for the future life of generations. The second concept which is still related is the concept of building the earth (*e'mar al-ardh*), which is also known as development, or the conception of creating a human civilisation on earth, which has been described in detail by Muslim scholars, especially the Andalusian scholar, 'Abd al-Rahman Ibn Khaldun (d. 1406 AD) and others. Justice and kindness to others (*al-'adl wa'l-ihsan*), are essential for human civilisation, including the general welfare currently carried out and play a role for future generations (Hossain, 2019; Qadir & Zaman, 2019).

The third aspect relevant to sustainability in the Qur'an is avoiding waste (Israf, al-A'raf, 7:31) and waste (*al-tabdzir*, QS al-Isra', 17-27). However, technical differences have been drawn between them where both are identical. Israf means waste and waste of what is permissible, such as people who consume excessive food or use water wastefully, even for cleanliness, and the primary function is purification (*wudhu*). Apart from that, the concept of "tabdzir" on the other hand means spending on things that are haram in the first place, such as buying drugs and destructive gambling tools. In this regard, Allah ﷻ says, "Allah does not love prodigal sons – *al-musrifun*," and refers to the latter that they are "brothers of Satan," both expressions signifying primarily morals and behaviour.

Aspects of human behaviour can be the subject of legal action if this is an actual loss (*darar*). The legitimate government is then given the authority, under the concept of public interest (*maslahah*), and a just policy (*siyasaah 'adilah*), to impose restrictions on what is permissible and also to lift the prohibitions on what is reprehensible (*makruh*) in Islamic law (*Shari'ah*). Summarising from the hadith of the Islamic law that 'losses may not be inflicted or retaliated against Islam in principle will authorise individuals and society to take judicial action against persons and organisations, even the state, who are guilty of environmental pollution; damage and destruction (Ansari et al., 2012; Zafar, 2014).

Meanwhile, the Prophet ﷺ has also added in connection with this issue. As explained to green the earth that "whoever plants a tree, no human or creature of Allah ﷻ will eat it without being counted as alms from it." In another hadith explained more widely, the Prophet ﷺ said that if one hour is left before the last hour and a person has

a palm shoot in his hand, he should plant it. In another narration, Abu Barzah once asked the Prophet ﷺ: "Teach me something so that I can benefit from it." He said, "Remove the trash from the paths of the Muslims." Muslim leaders, such as the first caliph Abu Bakar *as-Shiddiq*, advised their troops to not cut down trees, destroy agriculture, or kill animals, except for essential human needs when engaged in war with enemy forces.

Furthermore, one could elaborate further, but even from what has been said, it is clear that sustainability, moderation and cleanliness are embedded in the teachings of Islam and are an integral part of the faith of the Muslims. Rich and resourceful as these sources are, many aspects of these teachings are overlooked in general's personal behaviour, speech, and lifestyle (Anjum & Wani, 2018; Islam, 2004).

2.8 The Relationship between Islamic Sustainable Behaviour and Happiness

According to Seligman (2005), happiness is when a person feels more pleasant events than what actually happened, forgetting more about evil occurrences. Individuals must have experienced pressure in life that made them feel sad in their lives, like what happens in the process of life stages in achieving dreams in the future. The emergence of feelings of worry in oneself will cause individuals to feel unhappy. This is vulnerable to adolescents in the final level of high school. Teenagers will begin to think about the future choices that will be made. So that adolescents begin to make efforts to achieve goals or expectations in the future (Santrock, 2007).

Meanwhile, to remember that Late adolescence is a period at the stage of transitioning to adulthood, starting to enter the college level. Adolescents will be more aware of their abilities and realistic about expectations in the future (Hurlock, 1980). The existence of hope that will be achieved in reaching the end will make teenagers more selective and careful in choosing the business they will do. Happy teenagers will have positive relationships with friends, family, and society. In addition, happy teenagers will tend to have optimistic behaviour in living an enormous life. This is different from unhappy adolescents; they will be vulnerable to behavioural problems due to various risk factors, such as problems with individual characteristics, family, dropouts from school and violence (Murray, 2003).

Happiness is influenced by two factors, namely external factors and internal factors. External factors that affect happiness are money, marriage, social life, health, religion, age, education, climate, race and gender. Meanwhile, internal factors affecting

happiness are behaviour strength, satisfaction with the past, optimism about the future and delight in the present. One of the internal factors that significantly affect happiness is the strength of character (Diener, 2009).

According to Peterson & Seligman (2004), behaviour strength is a positive trait consisting of good behaviour (virtue) raised by individuals to deal with environmental problems. The strength of this behaviour is increased when the individual is in a specific complicated situation so that the individual will try to survive by showing the behaviour that makes the individual able to survive. When a problematic situation can be faced, the individual will achieve happiness.

The strength of personal behaviour in individuals can be seen based on the developmental tasks undertaken. One of them is in adolescence. In adolescence, there are six strengths of the most prominent behaviour. These six behaviour strengths are in different virtues. The most notable characteristics in adolescents are curiosity, perseverance, love, group membership, prudence and optimism (Seligman, 2004).

Meanwhile, every human being would generally crave happiness and make it his life's goal. From here, he always tried to achieve it in various ways. Because happiness is a good and commendable thing, getting it must be by doing good and praiseworthy things. (Sukardi, 2005: 94). According to Al-Farabi, theoretically, every human being can easily do interesting and commendable things to obtain happiness if he intends to do so. Humans can take advantage of the powers that exist within themselves. Humans' inherent and unified powers can be trained continuously to do good and evil deeds so that everything they do can become a habit in their lives (Aziz, 2015).

Happiness is the noblest and culmination of all the dreams everyone wants to achieve. Happiness is a thing or condition that, even though it is challenging for everyone to achieve, tries their best to get it. If the person succeeds in obtaining it, he has reached life's perfection in the truest sense. Not everyone can achieve that perfection quickly. Because the model that can be called *as-sa'adah*, happiness, is the peak of goodness permanently attached to him. Many kinds of excellence are the goal of human beings. If someone has reached the pinnacle of honour, he no longer needs other worth because the additional integrity is still not perfect and needs further integrity (Rassool, 2021; Tenri Awaru et al., 2021).

According to Al-Farabi, there are four virtues that every human being has: these virtues will cause everyone to get true happiness, namely the happiness of the world and the hereafter. The four virtues are theoretical, thinking, moral, and creative through practical actions. Of the four virtues, the theoretical purity of man is the highest gift from Allah ﷻ given to him. Theoretical virtues can automatically lead humans to the highest goal in life, namely knowing Allah ﷻ by knowing the origin of nature and everything in it. According to Al-Kindi, happiness is not achieved by sensual desires but by attaining rational passions and desires in thinking, distinguishing and knowing their essence (Arjoon, 2000; Hackett & Wang, 2012).

Thus, genuine happiness for humans is not sensual pleasures but in the form of spiritual and divine satisfaction. This pleasure can be achieved if humans are close to Allah ﷻ so that their minds and souls are guided and pure from the stains of lust focused on worldly things. When humans feel the ultimate pleasure above all sensory pleasures that are easily measurable, that is real happiness. If one passes from his natural state to an unnatural state in that affected state, suffering occurs. On the other hand, if he moves from an artificial state to a natural state, pleasure occurs. Therefore suffering often occurs in people who are influenced out of their natural state. Meanwhile, happiness occurs when he returns to his natural state (McMahon, 2004).

Happiness is synonymous with enjoyment because it is impossible for people to be happy without feeling something delicious. And vice versa, the appreciation of pleasure will give birth to happiness. According to Al-Razi, pleasure is a break from suffering, so there is no pleasure except after suffering. Pleasure is a pleasant feeling, while suffering is a painful feeling. Feelings are the sensory influences of people who do sensing. The impact of a person due to sensing allows two things to happen: to remain in an affected state, which means he has changed from his natural situation or moved from a state of being involved, influenced by his natural consciousness (Tacey, 2004; McMahon, 2004).

According to Ibn Miskawaih, the happiness of every existence is at the core of his behaviour based on perfection and wholeness, namely in the ability to distinguish, think, and take wisdom. To achieve happiness, Ibn Miskawaih cannot be separated from the concept of wisdom he formulated; theoretical and practical wisdom. Whoever desires happiness must complete these two pearls of wisdom. Theoretical wisdom can

be obtained through the learning process to know all knowledge and all things that exist in nature so that he can see the endpoint of all these existences; Allah ﷻ. While practical wisdom can be obtained by studying moral books that educate the soul and birth to attitudes that reflect moral perfection. If a man can perfect these two pearls of wisdom, he will get perfect happiness (Tacey, 2004; Cohen, 2006).

Some views of scholars on the soul related to happiness concluded that philosophers such as Ibn Miskawaih, Al-Farabi, Ibn-Sina and Al-Ghozali view that true happiness occurs through the improvement of the practical part of the mind. According to Ibn Miskawaih, the highest satisfaction will only be realised if humans can develop tauhid. People who have reached this position will feel total pleasure with their senses and whose soul is shaken by lust. Humans must be subject to divine rules and regulations to subdue animal energy in daily behaviour. That is why the reasonable mind must rule over all the body's points and calm the animal energies. But if the practical sense is incapable of mastering and submitting to animal energy, it will neglect to attain the perfection that belongs to it and fall into suffering (Haque, 2004). This is the meaning of what Ibn Taimiah said that happiness and well-being of the soul can only be realised through *ubudiyah* and perfect love for Allah ﷻ. Before achieving life's happiness, one stage needs to be understood to know and understand it. This stage has a meaningful life. Without a significant life motivation, it is impossible for someone to feel the happiness of life (Haque, 2004; Sezgin, 2015).

According to Al-Farabi, a person will achieve happiness if his soul has arrived at its perfect form and remains in such a state forever. To come to the *as-sa'adah*, according to Al-Farabi, humans can try to get used to it and do good deeds to the next stage. The meaning of life is things someone sees as necessary, feels valuable, believed to be accurate and can be used as his life purpose. The importance of life serves as a guide and direction in a person's life journey, so he is challenged to fulfil it. So, happiness is actually a side effect of a person's success in fulfilling the meaning of his life. While the meaning of life itself depends on a person's ability to perceive something. The process of suitable perception is a pleasure, while the function of the wrong perception will lead to suffering (Gray et al., 2012).

Abu Hamid Al-Ghozali et al. (2015) says *al-sa'adah* is the highest good among other virtues. These virtues basically consist of four kinds, namely:

- The goodness of the soul, as this is a source of priority. The distinction can be achieved by utilising science, and philosophy, maintaining (maintaining) self-respect, courage, justice, etc.
- Physical goodness. That is health, strength, beauty, longevity, etc.
- Goodness from outside oneself consists of four things: wealth, kinship, glory, and honour.
- Goodness consists of four things: guidance of Allah ﷻ, His advice, getting the truth from Him, and fixing for him a stand.

Meanwhile, starting from individuals born in this world, entering infancy, childhood, adolescence, adulthood, and the elderly. Each stage of development passed by an individual throughout his life has various developmental tasks. Developmental tasks arise at or around a certain period of an individual's life which, if successful, will create a sense of happiness and lead to success in carrying out subsequent tasks. Entering the stage of adolescent development, namely the age of 13 to 18 years, adolescents begin to face new developmental charges. This, of course, requires adjustment because the teenager faces very significant changes. Among them are physical, interest and psychological changes. Meanwhile, the task of adolescent development not carried out in the previous period does not mean it is lost but is still carried over today (Petersen et al., 1988; Dunning et al., 2004).

Teenagers at the final high school level start planning for college. This often results in change and stress. But if the teenager already has goals and expectations to achieve, the teenager will try to make them happen. If the desired goals and expectations have been completed, the teenager will feel happy (Hurlock, 1980). Happiness is when a person feels more pleasant events than actually happened and forgets more about destructive occurrences. Happiness in adolescents arises from the fulfilment of needs that are under expectations. Requirements in adolescents include self-acceptance, conflict resolution independently, getting protection and love from the closest people and having views and efforts to achieve goals (Seligman, 2002; Hurlock, 1980).

Individuals who have happiness in their lives will have positive characteristics, such as self-respect, a sense of optimism, more openness, and being able to control themselves. Individuals who value themselves tend to accept their own circumstances.

The importance of optimism possessed by the individual will make the individual fight harder to get what he wants. In addition, if the individual is more open, they will interact a lot with many people and have positive relationships with others. Individuals who can control themselves can control their emotions well (Schneider, 2001; Doran, 1981).

Before reaching happiness, individuals are also influenced by several factors. Two factors can affect the emergence of joy; external factors and internal factors. One of the internal factors that influence the emergence of happiness is the strength of sustainable behaviour. The power of nature is good behaviour that directs individuals to achieve virtue or positive traits reflected in thoughts, feelings and behaviour (Park et al., 2004). The strength of this behaviour is good behaviour in the six shades of virtue (virtue). These six virtues consist of wisdom and knowledge, courage, humanity and love, justice, simplicity and transcendence. Situational theme Adolescents in their final year of high school tend to stress because they start thinking about college or realistic life goals. Strength of behaviour In dealing with problems at the end of high school, teenagers will show their behaviour. The power of consistency is delivered so the teenager can survive difficult situations. Happiness When the strength of sustainable behaviour raised can solve the problems at hand, the teenager will feel pleasure (Lickona, 2004; Seligman, 2012).

2.9 Happiness is one of the goals of *Sharia*

While happiness is meant here is a long-term effect that has a widespread impact caused by several influencing factors, as well as the economy, living conditions, and income growth, which help increase well-being, generally referred to as "more is better" (Easterlin, 2003). It is further explained that the components of happiness can be divided into three; Happiness consists of three distinct elements: a happy life, a good life, and a meaningful life (Sirgy & Wu, 2009).

Meanwhile, throughout civilisation, conventional ideas models which assume an ethical canon are myopic and flashy because they are based on their mortal inauguration belief in happiness. In comparison, happiness or epicureanism is sought based on the hope of pleasure. These ways usually anticipate ethical approaches that are sometimes separated from faith or through religion. On the other hand, the moral law accepted by religious beliefs often emphasises ideals that do not stress our presence in the macrocosm. Muslims maintain rules of conduct that are not time-bound or poisoned by mortal desires, reinforcing several essential factors of the Islamic ethical

system (Hassan, 2020; Zainuldin et al., 2018). In addition, the Islamic way of life emphasises the relationship between man and his Creator. Where through the conception of Islam, Allah ﷻ is Perfect and All-Knowing.

Opinions and conduct are adjudicated to be immorally tentative on the private intention. Allah ﷻ is Human and comprehends every meaning impeccably and fully. Good intents followed by good behaviour are meditated as deification in Islam. Legal (*halal*) intents can not make unlawful, and unlawful (*haram*) conduct can not make halal. Islam permits individuals the freedom to believe and act still they desire, but not at the cost of justice and responsibility. Belief in Allah ﷻ gives total individual freedom from anybody or anything except Allah ﷻ. Choices that benefit the nonage or maturity aren't basically ethical in themselves. So Islamic ethics isn't at each a figures game. Islam's sustainable attitude routines an open system to ethics, not a sealed, tone-acquainted system. Egoism has no provision in Islam (Al-Jallad, 2008; Antara et al., 2016).

Islamic ethical choices focus on a contemporary interpretation of the Quran and the natural world. Unlike the moral systems encouraged by several creeds, Islam inspires humankind to exercise *at-tazkiyah* (tone enhancement) through emotional involvement in the Islamic way of life (Booze & Maddox, 1992; Evans, 2011). By performing serviceably in the middle of the tests of worldly life, Muslims demonstrate their significance to Allah ﷻ. The Islamic ethical system is neither fractured nor uni-dimensional. It's a part of the Islamic view of life and thus complete. There's internal thickness or equilibrium (*'adl*), about which the Qur'an says Hence have we created of you a community (*ummah*) correctly balanced that you may be viewer throughout the countries and the Apostle a viewer over yourselves (Al Qur'an 2 – 143) (Hashi, 2011; Yasmeen, 2008).

Muslim's belief is considered a first because it gives the worldview that impacts the whole mortal persona-geste, tastes, lifestyle and preferences, and mindsets towards human beings, terrain, and coffers. It seeks to stimulate a balance between the spiritual and material urges of the mortal tone, enhance individuals, family and social solidarity, promote peace of mind in the human being and forestall the development of anomalies. A Muslim's faith delivers the moral sludge, which aims at keeping tone-centredness within the boundaries of social interest by varying particular preferences as per social

urgencies and eradicating or lessening the use of effects for the purposes that aggravate the realisation of the social vision. All these rudiments that fulfil the *maqashid al-Shariah* (neutrality of Islamic laws) and sustainable development fall within the conception of *Maqasid al Shairah* (Chapra et al., 2008).

2.10 Muslim Students Success as Sharia Goals

Accepting Challenges to Achieve Best Life Values

In devoting oneself as a servant of Allah in the world and making a Muslim's life productive here, it is necessary to make the values in life more meaningful, especially in carrying out the mandate as a Muslim. Where the task of intelligent beings has been given an excellent study in carrying out life in the world, as the word of Allah *Ta'ala*:

وَمَا خَلَقْتُ الْجِنَّ وَالْإِنْسَ إِلَّا لِيَعْبُدُونِ ﴿٥٦﴾

I did not create jinn and humans except to worship Me. (Adz Dzariyat: 56)

Through the verse, Muslims have been required from the beginning of their creation to worship Allah Almighty, and part of servitude to Allah other than monotheism is to carry out the mandate of Allah in the world as long as life is still in the human body. In addition, a Muslim has always been required to make his deeds always good (*shalih*) and can have an impact on those who are with him, as Allah *Ta'ala* has stated:

وَأَنْذِرْ عَشِيرَتَكَ الْأَقْرَبِينَ ﴿٢١٤﴾

And warn your near relatives. (QS As Shu'araa: 214)

Humans generally underestimate time so that it doesn't even have value because no improvement makes that time a value for humans. Apart from that, life values can only be obtained once, so it is imperative to see challenges and accept them to learn and achieve success. So that in making time meaningful, Muslims are required to complete the behaviour of Muslims expressive but also how to use time management. So here it has been mentioned as well in Quran:

وَالْعَصْرِ ﴿١﴾ إِنَّ الْإِنْسَانَ لَفِي خُسْرٍ ﴿٢﴾ إِلَّا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَعَمِلُوا الصَّالِحَاتِ وَتَوَّاصَوْا بِالْحَقِّ وَتَوَّاصَوْا بِالصَّبْرِ ﴿٣﴾

By the time (1) Indeed, mankind is at a loss, (2) Except for those who have believed and done righteous deeds and advised each other to truth and advised each other to patience. (3) (QS Al Ashr: 1 – 3)

In the use of time, humans have been given much time, which is rarely felt, especially for the millennial group who currently make time a very ordinary thing. Unlike the *Salaf* or earlier groups, where time is highly valued, it is related to human obligations in living life and adapting to the cycle of life. Time is an abstract thing but becomes the foundation of humans foundation in living and living; especially the essential thing for Muslims is the time of prayer, Hajj and Umrah, fasting and zakat, all of which are most crucial related to time, and Muslims must follow them in carrying out their duties essential worship. So it is necessary to go deeper into how to accept challenges and make them valuable as a form of servitude to Allah *Ta'ala*.

In addition to that, being a true Muslim who carries out orders from Allah and His Apostle will always be curious to understand things that are always found in the world, both in understanding true Islam and daily *muamalah* from personal and family as well as in society as well as curious in emphasising science as critical thinking for humans. It is illustrated in monotheism's journey from Ibrahim *Alaihissalam* in seeking his Lord from the sun and moon to finally understanding that they are all creatures and Allah is the Creator of the universe. Likewise, the science is told from the pious in the story of the Prophet Sulaiman, who can move the kingdom of Bilqis in the blink of an eye from Yemen to Sham. Of course, science has become a relationship that should be strong in Muslim behaviour in bringing up the why and how in interpreting everything in nature that can be learned. It is where the importance of being a lifelong learner in human behaviour lies.

Fig. 1, Creating Life Values Design

In creating life values based on the virtues of being a Muslim who is responsible for becoming a *Khalifah*, it is necessary to explain here through components that make life values more meaningful for themselves and can provide benefits for those around them:

1. Self-innovation

Developing self-innovation in each individual has significantly invested in noble personal development. Of course, the more innovative the individual is in seeing the problem and providing solution steps to keep him from falling from the brink of failure. Emotionally trained with innovation and moving through the process will make a solid personal asset who will always be hungry to learn the process and new things. The more innovations created in each individual, the stronger the individual's personality in living a noble character to interpret life values.

2. Self-scaling

With this component, each individual will be accustomed to making general and specific life skills, which are carried out daily, weekly and long term, creating a strong personality. Get acquainted with new things to start skills so that every person can master them quickly and precisely so that in the future, it will be easy to scale others, including family and relatives, to strengthen each individual's *Khalifah* personality.

3. Self-inspiring

With this component, each individual will be confident in strengthening self-awareness and personality and trying to transform the problem by progressing it by trying to find a way out without disturbing the people around, and independent in leading himself from interests, values and passion. The resulting habits will make the skills, knowledge and behaviour that are run daily become inspiration and motivation for themselves and energise others to have strong ambitions in creating life values.

Creating life values with the above components will provide self-development with a secure environment to continuously provide a positive magnet for oneself and those

around each individual. Developing these components will also strengthen steady productivity and provide output in producing various inspiring life values every day, ready to become lifelong learners and maintaining the *Khalifah* personality.

Confident Become a Lifelong Learner

In utilising time, Muslims need to understand their obligations to be leaders in their families. Of course, a fundamental capacity is required to guide families in practising a religion which is crucial here. Besides that, it also guides the family in carrying out a balanced life by teaching applied sciences that are generally needed in daily human life. In this case, Allah *Ta'ala* has also said:

وَإِذْ قَالَ رَبُّكَ لِلْمَلَائِكَةِ إِنِّي جَاعِلٌ فِي الْأَرْضِ خَلِيفَةً قَالُوا أَتَجْعَلُ فِيهَا مَنْ يُفْسِدُ فِيهَا وَيَسْفِكُ الدِّمَاءَ وَنَحْنُ نُسَبِّحُ بِحَمْدِكَ وَنُقَدِّسُ لَكَ قَالَ إِنِّي أَعْلَمُ مَا لَا تَعْلَمُونَ ﴿٣٠﴾

When your Lord said to the angels, “I am placing a successor on earth.” They said, “Will You place in it someone who will work corruption in it, and shed blood, while we declare Your praises and sanctify You?” He said, “I know what you do not know.” (QS Al Baqarah: 30)

The nature given to humans in the form of naming the *Khalifah* personality in themselves is certainly a crucial thing for Muslims themselves to lead in an empty state. Of course, it takes essential capacity to advance knowledge in guiding family and closest relatives, which has become an obligation for each individual (Maspul, 2022a; Tambak *et al.*, 2021). In addition, it has become a fundamental obligation that should be understood by Muslims in the obligation to pursue both religious and applied knowledge where the Messenger of Allah has said:

حَدَّثَنَا هِشَامُ بْنُ عَمَّارٍ، حَدَّثَنَا حَفْصُ بْنُ سُلَيْمَانَ، حَدَّثَنَا كَثِيرُ بْنُ شَيْظَرٍ، عَنْ مُحَمَّدِ بْنِ سَبْرِينَ، عَنْ أَنَسِ بْنِ مَالِكٍ، قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ - صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ - " طَلَبُ الْعِلْمِ فَرِيضَةٌ عَلَى كُلِّ مُسْلِمٍ وَوَضِعُ الْعِلْمِ عِنْدَ غَيْرِ أَهْلِهِ كَمُقَدِّدِ الْخَنَازِيرِ الْجَوْهَرَ وَاللُّؤْلُؤَ وَالذَّهَبَ " .

It was narrated from Anas bin Malik that the Messenger of Allah (ﷺ) said: "Seeking knowledge is a duty upon every Muslim, and he who imparts knowledge to those who do not deserve it, is like one who puts a necklace of jewels, pearls and gold around the neck of swine." (Sunan Ibn Majah 224)

In addition, in playing the caliphate in carrying out the mandate in the world, both in the family and in society, Muslims are asked not only to advise each other but also in

their role of competing in the goodness of one another, which will have a good impact on the community and be more sustainable in the future. in making life values at it best. Allah *Ta'ala* says:

فَاسْتَبِقُوا الْخَيْرَاتِ ۗ إِلَى اللَّهِ مَرْجِعُكُمْ جَمِيعًا فَيُنَبِّئُكُمْ بِمَا كُنْتُمْ فِيهِ تَخْتَلِفُونَ ﴿٤٨﴾

So compete in righteousness. To Allah is your return, all of you—then He will inform you regarding your differences. (QS Al Maaidah: 48)

It has become substantial for Muslims to live with knowledge so that they always walk in the corridors of Islam and can make life balance the goal of living as long as humans are in the world. Therefore, here Muslims must play two behaviours for themselves to proportionate the goals that will be achieved, namely:

1. Empower the Mindset

In acting out the need for personal and family leadership, it has become the basis for humans to develop a mindset of thinking in how to become a person who has wisdom in carrying out his personality and developing his capacity. Empowering the stand can be done in a work environment by attending non-degree lectures or even becoming a degree-seeking student. Developing a perspective is also needed to master religious and applied knowledge while being able to drive it in the appropriate Islamic corridor. In addition, it is also necessary to strengthen the scientific basis both from religion and application. This is crucial for Muslims, where seeking knowledge is a human need apart from the commands of Allah and His Messenger. They all have an essential circulation in developing perspectives and deepening critical thinking to strengthen Muslim behaviour with an appropriate and measurable foundation.

2. Grow the Asset and Resources to Lead

In expanding the mindset, it is also necessary to grow the assets and resources to lead, where with a commitment to studying itself, the outcomes can be an essential component to become a human asset in leading family and closest relatives to people who have communication and social relationships daily many of them. Assets owned include tangible and intangible, in addition to those that do not materialise. Such as the degree that has been achieved, which will help in navigating the following degree pathway to be taken next. Every day, of course, Muslims will

always grow uniquely and in different ways in managing assets and resources to become *Khaifah* (leaders) in all matters personally and with family and closest relatives.

In the making lifelong learning the primary commitment for Muslims, it is necessary to collect data from the personal capacity of humans through their ability to develop an empowerment mindset and grow the asset to lead, as described previously. In making it essential in the two cases above, here for Muslims, have been able to make themselves confident to become lifelong learners. Among them are in classifying through three challenges as described below in mitigating risk in self-improvement failure:

1. Self-Improvisational Risk

In everyday life, humans will find challenges in making each experience difficulty in improvising behaviour and energy in achieving the goals of a plan that has been prepared with a good mindset. In this case, each individual must cultivate improvisation daily to strengthen each behaviour, which needs to be maintained daily. In sustaining improvisation to mitigate the risks for individual Muslims, it can be done by starting time discipline from prayer times and following daily studies that have become routine online and offline. Apart from that, we can record data from the daily to-do list to avoid the improvisational risks that appear in the middle of the road every day; every individual can see this with laziness which is a common problem for every human being.

2. Self-Operational Risk

Meanwhile, from the perspective of each individual dealing with daily activities, there will always be challenges that allow the daily activities previously scheduled to fail to be carried out. This is with the emergence of risk both from personal internal dynamics with problems from health issues, anxiety, and others. Likewise, the emergence of external from each individual that emerges from the environment or relatives provides additional behavioural problems and negatively affects our daily self-operation. So it is necessary to return to the original intention and open the list that has been previously planned to make sure with the use of time whether each of the previously planned portions of the activity has received a reasonable and proportional daily achievement. Binding oneself with time and a written plan will help make it a solution to prevent self-operational risk from arising at any time for every Muslim individual.

3. Game-changing Risk

In addition, in making the daily behaviour following the plan-based that has been structured short and long term, both daily, weekly, and monthly, it is essential here to recap in mitigating game-changing risk which will appear at any time and destroy all plans. It is caused by the occurrence of a huge thing that has a sizeable negative effect on the self-improvement failure of each individual. For example, the inability to continue studying due to the collapse of the personal or family economy in funding studies is very often the case in middle to lower social communities at the level of third countries. Not only that, sometimes it arises from the personal externalities of each individual who gets a big disaster from the environment, for example, a natural disaster that appears suddenly.

In mitigating this game-changing risk for each Muslim, patience and prayer become the main focus in testing each Muslim's patience, which will provide a much better return in this world and the hereafter, as has been said by Allah Ta'ala. In addition, the Prophet received many tests that were far more severe than those who lived in the last days, and Allah had promised the best for the Messenger of Allah and his Companions and Islam itself until the end of time. In this case, the Muslim personality has been formed to be vital in mitigating game-changing risks at any time. Allah stated in Quran:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اسْتَعِينُوا بِالصَّبْرِ وَالصَّلَاةِ إِنَّ اللَّهَ مَعَ الصَّابِرِينَ ﴿١٥٣﴾

O you who believe! Seek help through patience and prayers. Allah is with the patient. (QS Al Baqarah: 153)

Reviewing Outcomes of Lifelong Learner Goals

In making success a measure of a Muslim's lifelong learner, here we need measurable and sustainable goals for Muslims themselves. Each of these will strengthen through the behaviour process of the individual to run according to the corridor to make it more measurable and run according to what is expected, desired, religious and personal. In maximising the activities of each individual, the goal will help in making the sustainability of the behaviour of each individual through the economy of society and the environment. Without individual personal goals, the path of their efforts and efforts will not be directed toward pursuing the path to success as lifelong learners (Maspul & Amalia, 2022).

Furthermore, it is also necessary to develop critical thinking and make the mediums and objectives measurable in determining lifelong learner goals. This is also done by always tracing all the actors with the why, what, and how, which are crucial in knowing the priority scale. Besides that, getting used to critical thinking will also make it easier for each individual to explore the needs of the individual and the community, converting problems into sustainable innovation. Personal resilience will be solid and able to analyse strongly in dealing with matters relating to the socio-economic and environment that will connect to his future to become a lifelong learner (Paul & Elder, 1990).

Meanwhile, in strengthening the lifelong learner goals, it is necessary to classify the goals themselves in each individual's personality. In this case, the needs and processes owned by each individual differ depending on each person's circle of affiliation, internal and external, such as economic status, family status, and position in the surrounding groups where all of them will not be separated from the personal resilience of Muslims in facing challenges in sustainability in their respective communities.

In addition, each individual has a different life cycle turnover in carrying out what percentage of daily activities both in the family atmosphere and work environment and its relation to other general levels of society. In addition, given the capacity of personnel to manage the process of the goal itself, it is necessary to classify the priority scale of the plans to be achieved, including the following:

1. Commit Goal

This goal is an absolute must be pursued and make a proportional and hooked set planning for each individual. Continuing online lectures is undoubtedly not the same as offline lectures due to each own pace in participating in the online lecture activities. This is also a challenge for many students who cannot complete college due to financial reasons or other things because of the lack of measurable discipline in setting up planning from the start of college. Another thing is also due to limitations in the ability to understand the structure of the syllabus that is already available, a lack of curiosity in learning other things related to the syllabus in other online resources.

The many challenges and gaps that arise from each individual must be mitigated as early as possible by making a setup plan which will be explained later. Commit

goals can be carried out well even if there is a risk of self-improvement failure because with habituation in time discipline and being able to divide the classification of basic daily needs from personal, both internal and external, in the family environment, this goal will be achieved accordingly.

2. Stretch Goal

As for this goal, it has the potential to be successful, and the achievement will be successful both in the short term and long term, depending on the resilience strength of each individual in facing the threat of obstacles and challenges from risk self-implementation. The resilience of each individual will be strongly related to the social economy and environment to carry out this goal, even though the timeframe is longer and due to the stretch with the condition of the Muslim individual so that it does not become a crucial thing to change the individual massively in behaviour but make it a reinforcement of the basic concept of the life of the individuals concerned.

On the other hand, it can be exemplified by managing daily activities that are not urgent but develop more profound into the personality and behaviour of individuals in online learning, such as MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses), which is currently much in demand by Muslim youth with self-paced learning and learning concepts that are structured from each of the world's universities. Coursera, LinkedIn Learning, and others are some MOOC models that are very good at practising time management rules for students and are accessible online anywhere and anytime (Daradoumis *et al.*, 2013).

Fig. 2, Lifelong Learner Goals Design

The two types of personal goals mentioned above can be the basics in making Muslims personally train in managing self-improvement in strengthening the *Khalifah* personality for each individual as the primary goal of becoming a Muslim in the world.

SMART Objectives Implementing a Strategic Plan for Effective Online Learning

In designing a strategy for the effectiveness of online learning, the term here can be borrowed through SMART objectives, which effectively achieve the goals described previously and help strengthen each individual's productivity (Bovemd'Eerd *et al.*, 2009). With SMART objectives, it will be easier to set goals, frame plans and mitigate existing risks. SMART here is the definition of five letters as described below:

1. Specific

Specifying what is achieved is very important in critical thinking in developing and designing greater possibilities in setting goals. This will not be separated from the what, why, where, when, and how of achieving the goal plan.

2. Measurable

Measuring the capacity of the goal plan is also a measure that is no less important in finding objectivity in aligning it with each individual's goal setup. This can be helped by quantitative methods where the number of sizes one wants to achieve can be aligned with numbers, such as how much it will cost to complete online learning programs, both degree and non-degree and how the cost payment system will be completed. Therefore, all cost sources used can be measured from the beginning of the program is followed until it is completed.

3. Reachable

In setting these goals, either stretch or commit goals must also be aligned with the ability to achieve them. Is this program following the major studied by the individual, or is it a cross major, which will later become an obstacle in its completion because it requires primary mastery that has never been taken before? Then how can each manage critical thinking about the process of completing this goal? It is also a crucial thing to think about as early as possible.

4. Relevant

The relevance of individual abilities must also be in line with the program to be followed, from answering why the online learning program is relevant and how it is related to individuals who participate in it. From the beginning, the logical framework has worked in aligning the relevance of the online learning program, which will have outputs that are not only appropriate but also strengthen the individual's personality in his overall personality.

5. Time-bounded

The last one is the suitability of the time in the completion of the program taken, which is crucial to recap all the cost-effectiveness and measure the program output from online learning, both degree and non-degree followed. Besides that, aligning with some critical thinking like what I will do today, tomorrow, next week and so on so that the program's achievements can be measured while taking the program from start to finish.

Each other has an attachment to their respective roles in helping behavioural Muslims in critical thinking to align online learning programs that will be taken from the beginning to the subsequent output. With the SMART above, it will help motivate individual Muslims in structuring the goals of each online learning program, both degree and non-degree. Likewise, it will focus on aligning with the goal setup, both commit and stretch, to mitigate risks arising from each Muslim individual's internal and external natural behaviour.

In addition, with time management, which is vital in aligning with SMART Objectives, with time for a Muslim, there will be a firm commitment as a basis for accountability in seeking *Khalifah's* personality from each individual. The existence of time management will also link the character of each Muslim in a uniform restructuring of daily activities with his resilience as a Muslim in the social economy and environment. Time management associated with the five SMART above can help develop principles rather than productivity which is inseparable from place, mind and time. Assist in the most incredible opportunity to grow and be more valuable in structuring life values at their best in each *Khalifah's* personality in every Muslim.

2.11 Conclusion

Sustainable Islamic behaviour that has been formed from belief/faith and through *maqashid al-Shariah*; provides space for Muslims to perform their behaviour to be proper and capture the goals of what Allah ﷻ wants. The goal in question is to form noble Islamic behaviour/morals; it will also positively impact themselves, and people who interact with people who behave/have sustainable Islamic behaviour in specific communities.

On the other hand, Self-realisation is a fundamental idea that impacts or shapes a teacher's teaching philosophy and practice. From the Islamic perspective, self-realisation also allows teachers to reflect on their culture, language, social norms and moral values; self-reflection teaches students with diverse backgrounds to understand and consider their differences (Yakovleva, 2022). Understanding and respecting cultural roots can help educators appreciate our Islamic students' cultural roots. One of my biggest struggles as a global teacher is adjusting the Islamic teaching philosophy according to Islamic students' cultural beliefs and social standards. I can work with various students from diverse backgrounds and cultures worldwide. One notably fantastic thing is the cultural diversity from student to student and country to country. For example, many researchers investigated Southeast Asian students' quietness and reluctance from the perspective of the region's culture and its influences on general education. I have also experienced that students are usually hesitant to ask questions or participate in the classroom for various reasons, such as fear of making mistakes, shyness, the impact of tradition and moral values, and fear of interrupting Muslim educators. Muslim educators tried to organise meetings with parents to spread awareness about implementing positive strategies to help students grow and learn without physically abusing them. It does not always work because some parents have their ways and reasons, but few are open to adopting positive strategies to foster a positive relationship with their children.

The Islamic philosophy and practice are mainly based on progressivism for some of Muslim educators. Creating a positive Islamic teaching and learning environment and build positive rapport with my students and their parents through communication and interaction (Passow, 1982). Ensuring that all students feel safe, welcome, loved and cared for in classroom. Muslim educators and people developed a Muslim student-centred classroom where all the Muslim students can learn and not hesitate to make mistakes. Empowered learners are the ones who are curious, find the

content interesting, and can relate the content to their personal experiences or real-life situations. Developing a solid relationship/ bond with an individual is the foundation to empower learners to become engaged.

Meanwhile, one of the ways to identify and address students' diverse backgrounds in some teaching practices is by introducing multiculturalism activities as core values in Islamic sustainable behaviour. The art classroom can be a place to explore personal and cultural aspects of life by having students explore their heritage through art or look. Some use multiculturalism activities in Islamic youth student society because they greatly enhance student engagement and involvement by celebrating their individuality and environment, especially in a diverse classroom (Kennedy, 2006). Muslim students can draw or collect things specific to their culture to put in a cigar-size box—for example, clothing, family photos, flags, customs, etc. Besides that, the need to understand one character and another in interaction makes it crucial to placing problems on each side of one or the other Muslim students. Some can apply this in the last period so that Muslim educators are expected to be wise in understanding students and instilling the goals they want to achieve.

Moreover, the box will serve as a cultural map to the viewer. At the end of the task, each Muslim student can share their chest with the whole class, which will enhance the positive environment in the classroom by knowing about each other's culture and will strengthen the relationship bond (Jones, 1976). Besides, some Muslim educators observed Muslim students closely to understand how they behave, respond and react to different situations in their unique society. Muslim educators needed to approach an Islamic teaching philosophy and practices according to cultural diversity and social standards without imposing other ideas, beliefs and values. A Muslim teacher could remain neutral, especially in a foreign country. Muslim educators are responsible for students' academics and teaching them ethical and social values. Muslim students are a reflection of a teacher, and therefore it is the teacher's responsibility to ensure that their Muslim students become thriving and sustainable citizens in the future.

Meanwhile, as Muslim youth get inculcated into society through Islamic socialisation, they learn and develop some traits essential for their success in Islamic education. Culture is a significant factor influencing children's education across different communities; a word for the way of life of groups of people, the behaviour, beliefs, values, and symbols they accept, generally without thinking about them. I have realised that the success of education in a child is not solely dependent on how much

impact the teacher is willing to put into it but also on the traits the students have to exhibit - such as Islamic hard work, resilience, determination, positive mindset, and optimism.

How positive sometimes the Islamic personal traits have influenced Muslim students' success. Where the confidence in the concept of thinking can empower the mindset that everyone will be able as long as they have the desire and growing resources to lead with knowledge as well as explore challenges that will be encountered through self-improvisational and self-operational risks and game-changing risks to review outcomes from lifelong learner goals. Qualities such as hard work in a sustainable way often significantly impact Muslim students' results, especially in utilising technology in self-innovation, self-scaling and self-inspiring.

Furthermore, it's been engaged to students that working hard prepares them for more complex tasks. Students who grow up in families or societies that believe and stress hard work as an essential tool for success thrive better in classes. Such students attend classes, do their homework, read, and participate more. As Hyo-jin (2022) stated, South Korea achieved 98 per cent literacy among its citizens due to societal belief in hard work. Moreover, humans possess the trait of laziness and prefer the most economical way possible if they have to do things. Hence, there is a need for social pressure, emerging from the belief system that stresses the importance of children having to cope with the responsibility of getting up early before school hours, attending classes, studying their lessons and doing the assignments given, and respect for teachers and concentration in class and many more. This will facilitate children's education with the limited time available to teach them. It is often agreed that students perform better when the teacher is flexible, knowledgeable, and skilled. On the other hand, its necessary teachers will also serve better when Muslim students are well-behaved and exhibit positive academic traits. The role of Muslim educators can change the world, starting from the small community around them and consistently wanting to change society for the better. With this good intention, little by little, based on strength, we can overcome social and political gaps everywhere.

CHAPTER THREE – RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3. Research Methodology

This research uses quantitative research. The data analysis approach used in this study is a statistical data analysis technique to determine The Role of Islamic Sustainable Behavior on the Happiness of Islamic High School Students of Ibnu Umar, South Tangerang. This research method is the correlation method, which is a method to examine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables; the data collection techniques in this study use several techniques, namely questionnaires, observations, and interviews.

Calculation of correlation using Product Moment; where a technique to find the correlation between two often used variables. This correlation technique was developed by Karl Pearson. To determine how far the influence of Islamic sustainable behaviour (variable X) on students' happiness (variable Y) was carried out using the Karl Pearson Product Moment formula. This research was analysed using correlation analysis techniques, coefficient of determination test and t-test, explained through the correlation Test.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{(x^2) \cdot (y^2)}}$$

$$x^2 = (x - \bar{x})^2$$

$$y^2 = (y - \bar{y})^2$$

$\sum xy$ = the number of times x and y .

Explanation:

r_{xy} = The index number correlating " r " is the product-moment.

x^2 = Number of deviation score " x " after the first squared.

y^2 = Total deviation score " y " after the first squared.

The researcher uses the product-moment analysis technique to determine whether there is any correlation between sustainable Islamic behaviour in achieving happiness among SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan students.

The population in this study was 17 students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan. The author shall describe the research object in chapter III on the data presentation stage. With the total population of the above in mind, the author concluded that the research should be implemented by taking the population of students as a whole. Determination of

the above study population follows Arikunto's opinion (2002: 107), "is a mere shadow when the subjects amount to less than 100 (one hundred) it is better to just take them all, so the research represents the study population. Furthermore, if the subject is more than 100 (one hundred), it can be taken between 10-15% or 20-25% or more." (Arikunto 2002)

3.1 Method of Data Collection and Data Analysis

A. Method of Data Collection

The author chose the fourth method to determine the extent of the role of Islamic sustainable behaviour in performing Toward Happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan. According to the data collection framework, the author uses the questionnaire, observation, interview, and documentation methods. To obtain factual data, the author has carried out the data collection as follows:

1. Method of Observation

"Observation is an activity focusing on an object by using all senses such as sight and hearing, etc." (Arikunto 2002) Observations in this study are using non-systematic observation methods or not using the guidelines as an instrument of obedience. The observation method is used to observe events and support and complement the questionnaire.

2. The Questionnaire

The questionnaire method is several written questions used to obtain information from respondents regarding reports about him or other matters that he knew. (Arikunto 2002) The way a questionnaire is to be answered can be of two, namely:

- a) Open questionnaire, allowing respondents to answer in their own terms and language.
- b) The enclosed questionnaire; is a questionnaire that provides answers so that respondents may only choose.

The author used the enclosed questionnaire method to consider matter, mind, energy, and time in this study.

3. Method of Interview

"An interview is what is commonly known as a list of questions asked and the dialogue conducted by the interviewer to obtain information." (Arikunto 2002) The author has used this method to obtain data about the students' behaviours in seeking happiness, specifically around the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.

4. Method of Documentation

The author collected data using quotes, analysis, and obtaining information documented by SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan students to find and manage the research object's identities to strengthen the data.

B. Data Analysis

“Data analysis is the most complex and mysterious of all of the phases of a qualitative project, and the one that receives the least thoughtful discussion in the literature” (Thorne 2000). “Analysis of the data is a series of reviewing, grouping, interpreting and verifying data so that a phenomenon has a social, academic and scientific value.” (Tobroni 2001)

Analysis of the data used in the research on the impact of the Islamic sustainable behaviour in performing on students' happiness is a quantitative one using the product-moment formula:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{(x^2) \cdot (y^2)}}$$

$$x^2 = (x - \bar{x})^2$$

$$y^2 = (y - \bar{y})^2$$

$\sum xy$ = the number of times x and y .

Explanation:

r_{xy} = The index number correlating “ r ” is the product-moment.

x^2 = Number of deviation score “ x ” after the first squared.

y^2 = Total deviation score “ y ” after the first squared.

The author uses the product-moment analysis technique because the author wanted to determine whether there is any correlation between the role of Islamic Sustainable Behavior Toward Happiness Among Students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.

3.2 Planning of Research

Research as a scholarly activity refers to a planned, systematic, steady, sourced system from accurate and reliable data and results in a viable study that is presentable. And so the author shall report and explain matters relating to field activities that include:

1. Preparation Phase

At this stage, the author described various things about the preparation in reporting research results. And they are as follows:

1. Submit the title and then consult further issues related to the research title. Such as the preparation of the background of the case, the aim of the study, and formulation of the problem use of the study, on the other hand, reasons for choosing the title, the limit of terms in the title, the scope of the discussion, and postulate (assumption), hypothesis, research methods and systematic discussion. The author also conducted a previous concise study concerning the research title and performed library research from various sources relating to the matter being addressed in preparing this scientific paper. This culminated in a literature review.
2. The author created a consent form to ask permission to observe at school and its students and conduct research to write about The Role of Islamic sustainable behaviour toward happiness among students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan and research the correlation between both topics.
3. The author filed a written request to the principal of the SMA Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan to conduct this research on all related to the topic.
4. The author made a data collection structure.

- a. Observation

The author used observation to support the research in understanding the students' happiness and its implementation in the role of Islamic sustainable behaviour. The author uses the observation without using a routine, merely paying attention to the events occurring at school activities. Regarding topic selection or material, setting the aim, using methods and evaluation techniques without using the existing system. Through this, the author hopes to discover how Islamic sustainable behaviour improves happiness among students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.

- b. Questionnaire

The author compiled a questionnaire based on the written research and prepared ten-question items relating to Islamic sustainable behaviour and its implementation. Similarly, the author also gathered ten-question things on matters about happiness. Through these questionnaires, the researcher hopes to determine how Islamic sustainable behaviour supports happiness at their school and impacts it. The author also used the multiple choices method, giving three alternative answers. Great answers referred to those that indicate Islamic sustainable behaviour helps students' happiness a lot, correct answers refer to those that suggest Islamic sustainable behaviour helps happiness somewhat, and weak responses refer to those that

indicate Islamic sustainable behaviour has little to no impact on students' happiness.

Below is the scoring mechanism per answer category, namely:

- a = Great Answer receives a score of 3 (three)
- b = Good Answer receives a score of 2 (two)
- c = Weak Answer gets a score of 1 (one)

c. Interview

After the author prepared the interview technique, interviews with the students at the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan were conducted to obtain the data supporting the research process. Through these interviews, the researcher hopes to determine whether participants see Islamic sustainable behaviour positively impacts happiness in school outcomes.

d. Documentation

The author used the method of documentation as a reinforcement of existing techniques. The author collected all the data and documents on the study's subject or object in the documentation method and satisfying current routines.

2. Implementation Phase

After going through the stages of preparation, the author moved to the next step, the implementation phase, which consists of providing the questionnaires to the respondents, collecting the answered questionnaires, tabulating the data that has been entered, and giving a score on each item response accordingly.

1. The author distributed questionnaires to students on the role of Islamic sustainable behavior toward happiness and allocated sufficient time to complete the questionnaire.
2. The author collected the questionnaires, which contained the answers of the respondents.
3. To determine whether there is any correlation between the role of Islamic sustainable behavior toward happiness among students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan and whether participants agree that Islamic sustainable behaviour supports their happiness, data analysis must be carried out. After the questionnaires were collected, the author tabulated the data and marked the entry by giving scores on each of the existing items. Moreover, coupled with the observation of each questionnaire that uses enter from the respondents.
4. The author interviewed the students to know their behaviour in implementing the daily activities and whether they could improve their behaviour positively.

5. Collecting other data relating to outcomes of Islamic sustainable behaviour implementation and other files.

3. Data Presentation Stage

After undergoing the two previous stages, the third stage, the data presentation stage, the author presented the data in written form and described matters pertaining to the research object, the role of Islamic sustainable behaviour toward happiness among students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.

4. Object Research

The ones that become the object of research are the students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan, 17 students as a whole, and observed in terms of their activities such as;

- School activities
- Tahfidz Quran
- Extra curriculum

3.3 Data Analysis

The data determined from studies presented in previous chapters have not yet proven the hypothesis. For that to occur, information needs to be processed and analysed further. In this case, the author shall use the product-moment analysis technique when analysing the questionnaires, with the following formula:

1. $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum x}{N}$

2. $\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum y}{N}$

3. $x^2 = (x - \bar{x})^2$

4. $y^2 = (y - \bar{y})^2$

5. Correlation $r_{xy} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{(x^2).(y^2)}}$

Explanation:

- a. r_{xy} = Coefficient between x and y
- b. $\sum xy$ = number of results x and y
- c. x^2 = amount of deviation squaring x
- d. y^2 = amount of deviation squaring y

Before the formula is used, a preparation table with the following steps must be prepared in this fashion:

- a. Number the subject (respondent)
- b. Sum the score values by calculating the mean of variable X X
- c. Finding the score variable Y by calculating the mean Y
- d. Calculate the deviation of each score X and Y
- e. Squaring the deviation x
- f. Squaring the deviations y
- g. Multiplying variables x with variables y (xy)

A qualitative research methodology drew themes from the conversations and observations to analyse the interviews and observations to understand participant perspectives and shared activities. Besides the quantitative research, the research also used a qualitative research type with an exploratory design. The focus of research that is the centre of attention is the use of Islamic sustainable behaviour. This study's primary data source is research respondents who are considered to know and understand precisely Islamic sustainable behaviour on its impacts positively on students' happiness.

In this study, the instruments used an in-depth interview guide with a recorder, observation sheets, and a documentation checklist. Meanwhile, the data collection uses interviews, observation, and documentation of conditions in the field. In addition to that, the discussion used open-ended questions verbally to respondents. After collecting the data, the validity of the data was checked using the triangulation technique. The last stage is the data analysis stage which consists of data collection stages, data reduction, data presentation, and data verification.

The qualitative questions include how respondents think about sustainability and its challenges in practising Islamic behaviour and the role of Islamic sustainable behaviour toward happiness among students of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan. Then ask for an opinion on the students' experience related to school activities in SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan. The data obtained were analysed for their contents to bring different themes, tabulate them to be explored, categorised, and get articles to find the conclusion.

To strengthen this research, the author must explain several other discussion objects. It describes in further detail this research in its execution process, including;

1. Description of the beneficiary population includes articulating why and how the chosen population was determined and consulted in the project design.

To succeed in this research project, the author must classify the participant population correctly to get results that match this research title. Then the author

searched through digital search data and found several significant Islamic sustainable behaviour based on this research. Therefore, the recipient population must be identified by reference to the following characteristics: Indonesian male and female students studying at the senior high school level at the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan.

The direct beneficiaries are the students since they are the ones who can learn and apply the research. Beneficiaries also include those who were impacted by the project. In terms of intersectionality, there is no intersectionality in this research.

2. The description of a communications plan included how the project findings were shared or communicated, with whom, and for what purpose.

In this communication plan, certain stages can be performed suitably, including;

- a. Communication planning: The author provided sufficient information to participants/respondents on research related to the study. In this case, this can be done in several ways, including by e-mail, telephone, or directly visiting respondents who are connected with this research.
- b. Information distribution: The author set the appropriate time to sustain time management more proper, both for the author and the respondent. After compiling the questionnaire and the interview questions' arrangement, in this case, a short time frame was formed to make it more effective and less repetitive.
- c. Performance Reporting: In the data collection process, the author took the easy way to observe the interview results and the questionnaire that took place through personal visits, and other options available using telephone and e-mail were more efficient time sought. This is to maintain communication and design the reports at a suitable time.
- d. Manage respondent: In the expectation of building a good connection and carrying appropriate conclusions on the research, in this case, the author maintained communication with the respondent from the inception to the achievement of this research project. This communication plan is sustained weekly as an initial reference but does not rule out extraordinary communication outside of the week via text or call.

Once complete, the researcher shares the final results with the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan student. Sharing the study aims to randomly inspire the local community and global beneficiaries to incorporate the knowledge into their own

publications or practices. This research is transmitted via e-mail or other means if necessary.

3. List or discuss stakeholders involved in the project, either directly or indirectly, and a statement of how they were consulted in the project's design, goals, and outcome.

To place and classify stakeholders, it would be better if the author here uses a priority scale to communicate more, as described below;

1. High power, highly interested people: They are the most fully engaged respondent in communication and observation; as they are students at the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan, they make the most outstanding efforts to accomplish the research. The student participants are an example of this category.
 2. High power, less interested people: Some are involved in the school and policymakers, including the teachers. People who work at the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan but do not directly research are examples of this category.
 3. Low power, highly interested people: parents that adequately inform and talk to them to ensure no significant issues arise. They can often be helpful with the detail of the project. Communicating to them can be via e-mail; the latest information has been sent about the research to respond appropriately. Parents are low power because they cannot make decisions at the school but are highly interested in developing their children's behaviour using their service and learning more about it.
 4. Low power, less interested people: Muslim community with a common interest in Islamic behaviour and sustainability. Anyone stated as Muslim who can benefit from the research could be in this category.
4. Statement of potential risks for the project, including its outcomes or participants including the ways such risks are intended to be mitigated.

This research has risks caused by the author or the respondent as the research object. The author tried to complete this research to produce a relevant report such as what was performed below, both for risk or for solution steps that stem this risk. Those who are at stake in this research project include;

- a. The author lacks more extensive knowledge of Muslim behaviour and the Islamic environment, specifically regarding the three bottom legs of sustainability in the form of Islamic perspectives.
- b. Lack of time to conduct an extensive literature review, not enough existing information

- c. Lack of time to go through the process phase of completing research on time
- d. Limitations of the respondent in being open to providing information for completing this research.
- e. The limitations of respondents in their knowledge of Islamic behaviour, sustainability and the science of human behaviour.
- f. Limited costs in transportation and communication to complete the data taken from respondents.

The mitigation that can be carried out to solve this research includes;

- a. Explore the literature discussed in the study,
 - b. Seeking enlightenment through mentors and lead supervisors to find terms that are difficult to understand.
 - c. Communicate to the respondent well on the background to the purpose of this research.
 - d. Assisting respondents in opening discussion spaces on Islamic behaviour and its sustainability among the Muslim community.
 - e. Make use of all digital space for communication and data retrieval, which is related in this research from respondents and whoever has relevance.
5. A statement of where the student expects the project to be in 3-5 years and its intended long-term impacts.

Research in Islamic behaviour and sustainability will always be discussed in all stakeholders' laps in various areas. Primarily with the SDG's goals carried by the UN to promote sustainability in every part of human activities. The emergence of Islamic culture and behaviour regarding its sustainability turns that mutually benefit one another will raise research projects in this scope. From the stated background, I believe this research has advantages and virtues in advancing the Muslim community and all people.

5. Profile of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan

This Islamic school is a full-day school that implements a curriculum from national education and early Islamic primary education taught from elementary to high school, plus a methodology for memorizing the Quran. The school founded in 2009 in the city of South Tangerang (Tangerang Selatan), has produced many generations of Quranic men and women from various cities in Indonesia who have supported the management of this school. With the hope that the outcomes of graduates can memorise the Quran with a minimum of 9 juz of Quran fluently. In addition, graduates are expected not only to pass the curriculum

provided by the government but also to become a pious generation who can become future leaders in the Islamic community. Some of the activities that fill the weekly activities of the students such as self-defence, horse riding and swimming, English and Arabic clubs, and so on.

6. Implementing Hybrid Learning Process in Islamic High School Ibnu Umar Students South Tangerang

The occurrence of the global Covid-19 pandemic requires all educational institutions to apply digital learning models to maintain the quality of education. The home learning policy instructs by the government to all educational institutions, especially in Indonesia, indirectly obliges teachers and students to adapt to these changes. Islamic High School Ibnu Umar, South Tangerang, implements digital learning, namely hybrid learning, in the learning process during the pandemic and entering a limited face-to-face learning period while still following government policies. Implementation is defined as the implementation or application of something well planned. The implementation consists of three stages: planning, implementation, and evaluation.

Teachers' preparations for implementing hybrid learning are in two planning stages: limited face-to-face learning and online learning simultaneously during the learning process. In the planning stage, the teacher must provide a component, pedagogic competence, to plan, implement, and evaluate the learning assigned to him. Little face-to-face and online planning documents are prepared by teachers in stages, in the form of preparing lesson plans and further understanding supporting document files. The implementation of face-to-face learning is limited; besides preparing learning documents, little face-to-face learning is performed by limiting the number of students who come to school. Technically, students are divided into two groups, with a learning system of 50% following limited face-to-face learning and 50% taking online learning from home simultaneously. Teachers were initially equipped to use the online learning system easily; this was made more accessible by the direct involvement of teachers in preparing everything to run this online learning system. Online learning uses various platforms: WhatsApp, Google Classroom, Google Meet, and Zoom.

The hybrid learning model's implementation stage covers the duration of the teaching and learning process, the platform used, strategies, methods, media, and teaching materials the teacher prepares in the learning process. The implementation of learning is carried out every day from Monday to Saturday. Various platforms such as google classroom, google meet, zoom, and other applications are used for learning. The teaching

materials used in education are essential materials from each KD (basic competencies) using the google classroom application, google form, and other applications. The methods used by teachers are various approaches to bring learning materials, namely by lecture methods, question and answer, discussions, exercises, assignments, projects, etc.

The instruments used to assess attitudes, knowledge, and skills include attitude assessment through observation, peer assessment, journals, written tests and assignments, and skills competency assessment through practical examinations, projects and portfolios. The evaluation or assessment stage of hybrid learning includes authentic assessment, self-assessment, project assessment, daily test, mid-semester test, and end-semester test. Teaching and learning activities are carried out from Monday - to Friday, both online and hybrid, where teaching and learning activities start from 7.15 to 12.00 (originally from 7.15-14:55). For Arabic language subjects, only two-hour lessons are taught a week. In addition, 1 hour of subjects is 30 minutes during the pandemic, whereas 1 hour of topics was 40 minutes prior. Thus, to maximize all incoming issues with a limited time allocation to be more effective.

Meanwhile, in supporting Arabic learning, a *hifdzul mufrodat* (memorising Arabic vocabulary) activity has been carried out, which is carried out before teaching and learning activities from 7.15 - 7.30. In addition, for the delivery method when online, each student will share it with *mufrodat* (vocab) and its meaning through the WhatsApp Group of each class, along with examples of readings via voice notes. Overall, in overseeing the success of this activity, the role of OSIS (intra-school student organisations) is beneficial where the *takmir* is responsible but is still guided by the OSIS teacher/supervisor.

In addition, in the *tahfidz* learning method, for the initial level (class XI) in the first year, students are not allowed to memorize but to improve reading first for the first three months. After the assignment has been categorized as good, the students learned it while still being listened to (*talaqqi*) first by their respective tutors; as for the memory target, including 3 juz in three years, where every 3 months, there is an oral exam through the following verse advanced method. In addition, every 3 months, there is the best *tahfidz* reward program and khatam al-Qur'an rewards to motivate students to be more enthusiastic in this additional activity. Additional programs to familiarise students with reading the Qur'an, including recitations of the Qur'an, which are done three times in ten minutes (during offline teaching and learning activities) while online, the time is not bound or free. To help fill other activities, additional programs are needed, including; an internal student

competition held once every year, including the following competitions: speech in Arabic and memorising the Qur'an/Juz.

Limited face-to-face and online learning using a hybrid model are the best choices to start learning activities after the pandemic, with uncertain time developments and the absence of certainty. The implementation of hybrid learning in learning at SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan has several stages carried out by teachers, including planning, implementing and evaluating teaching assessments. In limited face-to-face learning, teachers prepare to learn tools and in online learning planning, teachers direct students through applications with internet networks available in academic units. Some of the advantages of using a hybrid learning model include teachers can describe positive involvement with students in class and some students who take part in learning at home simultaneously. Teachers and educational units can use the advantages and disadvantages of the hybrid learning model to carry out learning adapted to current conditions. The participation of all citizens of the education unit is significant. There is a need for good cooperation and communication to organise the expected learning conditions.

CHAPTER FOUR – DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH REPORT

4. Data Analysis and Results of the Research Report

4.1 Questionnaire Results

After the collected data is allocated into the table, it is further analysed to prove the proposed hypothesis. Then the deviation of each score is calculated with the formula, and the use of each deviation, after it is inserted in the product moment, is as follows:

Table I
Table For The Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

N	X	Y	X	Y	x ²	y ²	xy
1	28	21	1.65	1.24	2.71	1.53	4.14
2	30	19	1.76	1.12	3.11	1.25	3.89
3	25	19	1.47	1.12	2.16	1.25	2.70
4	30	29	1.76	1.71	3.11	2.91	9.06
5	30	28	1.76	1.65	3.11	2.71	8.45
6	28	24	1.65	1.41	2.71	1.99	5.41
7	28	22	1.65	1.29	2.71	1.67	4.54
8	30	29	1.76	1.71	3.11	2.91	9.06
9	30	23	1.76	1.35	3.11	1.83	5.70
10	30	22	1.76	1.29	3.11	1.67	5.22
11	22	22	1.29	1.29	1.67	1.67	2.80
12	29	19	1.71	1.12	2.91	1.25	3.64
13	25	21	1.47	1.24	2.16	1.53	3.30
14	28	23	1.65	1.35	2.71	1.83	4.97
15	24	21	1.41	1.24	1.99	1.53	3.04
16	30	24	1.76	1.41	3.11	1.99	6.21
17	30	27	1.76	1.59	3.11	2.52	7.86
Total	477	393	28.06	23.12	46.67	32.05	89.98

- a. $N = 17$
- b. $X = \frac{\sum x}{N} = \frac{477}{17} = 28.06$
- c. $Y = \frac{\sum y}{N} = \frac{393}{17} = 23.12$
- d. $\sum x^2 = 46.67$
- e. $\sum y^2 = 32.05$
- f. $\sum xy = 89.98$

Furthermore, the above results are incorporated into the product-moment formula as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_{xy} &= \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{(x^2) \cdot (y^2)}} \\
 &= \frac{89.98}{\sqrt{(46.67) \cdot (32.05)}} \\
 &= \frac{89.98}{\sqrt{1495.45}} \\
 &= \frac{89.98}{38.67} \\
 &= 2.32
 \end{aligned}$$

After the testing and analysis of the data, the author interprets the results so they can be measured in two ways:

1. Match with the conservative value table

Table II
Table of Conservative Value

Sizes	Interpretation
0.800 – 1.000	High correlation
0.600 – 0.800	Quite correlation
0.400 – 0.600	Rather low correlation
0.200 – 0.400	Low correlation
0.000 – 0.200	Very low correlation (not correlated)

2. Matching the values of “r” (the price of criticism of the importance of r product-moment)

As for the price table’s criticism, the product-moment correlation for N = 17, i.e. for a 95% significance level is 0.448 and a 99% significance level of 0.457.

Table III
Table of the Price of Criticism of the Value of r Product Moment

N	Interpretation 95%	Interpretation 99%
17	0.448	0.457

By matching the values in these tables for the product-moment, the correlation coefficient value of 17 is a 95% significance level for 0.448 and a 99% significance level for 0.457. Meanwhile, the results were obtained from calculations for 2.32, so the product-moment correlation significance level analysis was more significant than 95% and 99% significance levels.

4.2 Interview Results

The author met numerous respondents on Islamic sustainable behaviour in this interview session. Asking about Islamic sustainable behaviour and how they can help their beliefs become confident, the majority answered yes, especially about the happiness that arises from obedience. Obedience is their belief in Allah that Allah will promise the best to His servants. This is reinforced by their statement that every noble behaviour will be rewarded with glory; besides that, they also believe that Allah will give glory not only to them but also to give that glory to their parents. Several discussions related to their parents that each believed that if their children were entrusted with sincerity to Allah and Islam, then they would get the glory and not only they believed in this world and the hereafter. The author asks about the relationship between Islamic sustainable behaviour and the happiness they achieve, and they answer by acknowledging that there will always be a relationship between cause and effect from helping Allah's religion so that it will be easier for them in their daily lives in facing any challenge which leads to success and happiness.

Then when asked about their daily behaviour while at school, each of them made it not only for studying the world but also as a form of obedience to God; all respondents made this statement as one of their goals in finding a good personality that would produce outcomes in the form of happiness in their lives; the world and the hereafter. When asked about what challenges are usually encountered in carrying out this obedience, each respondent has different opinions, but the solution is patience in facing challenges that they believe will bring glory to that patience. The author assumes that with patience and fortitude that they fully hold tightly will make continuous good that results from one case to another.

Then about how they maintain their behaviour so that they are always consistent with obedience in seeking Allah's pleasure, all of them say that there is nothing that can make them compatible with compliance except by asking for help from Allah. In this case, the author makes one of these consistent statements in helping them not only want happiness as a goal but also to seek Allah's pleasure, where the relationship will be associated with *qadha* and *qadar*. From here, the author also believes that the sustainability of behaviour from Islamic perspectives that they manage in their behaviour is a form of worship that each respondent makes the sustainability of *ubudiyah* to Allah alone. This foundation is used as a firm grip on monotheism to God as God Almighty; from *Rububiyyah Uluhiyyah* and *al-Asma wa al-Sifaat*.

CHAPTER FIVE – CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

From the description of the research results, the author has conveyed his conclusion as follows:

- The role of Islamic sustainable behaviour significantly correlates to the happiness of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar students Tangerang Selatan, with pointed criticism that the price of labour $r = 2.32$ is above the 95% confidence level = 99% = 0.448 and 0.457. So that H1 (Working Hypothesis) reported Islamic sustainable behaviour contributed to impacting the existence of the happiness of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar students Tangerang Selatan, accepted. Moderate H0 (Null Hypothesis), which states Islamic sustainable behaviour doesn't contribute to impacting the existence of happiness of SMA Islam Ibnu Umar students Tangerang Selatan, is rejected.
- The role of Islamic sustainable behaviour is highly correlated when seen from the table with a conservative measure of the size ranges above 0.800 up to 1000.
- Based on the interview results with students and other stakeholders, from parents to school teachers at the SMA Islam Ibnu Umar Tangerang Selatan, they demonstrated their satisfaction in increasing the Islamic perspectives as tools to educate students in school for a better future Muslim leader in their community.

Suggestions

From conclusions that become exciting particularity ideas in research and development, especially at the school activities, the author provides suggestions including:

- It is a commonplace that Muslims today live in a time of extraordinary fitnah, especially in bringing Muslim youth to goodness; there will always be challenges. However, with the patience of all stakeholders in the success of Islamic education, it will make a positive impact and *istibaq al-khairat* of Islamic schools in the Indonesian Archipelago undoubtedly is what makes Islamic schools unique in Indonesia if they can maintain their consistency.

- The role of the general public in helping to maintain good Islamic behaviour is not only a familiar challenge but also a goal that we want to achieve to make Indonesia a *baldatun thayyibatun wa Rabbun Ghafur*. So it is appropriate to make monotheism (*at-Tauhid*) the basic foundation of all matters relating to the world and the hereafter in maintaining the pleasure (*ridha*) of Allah wherever and whenever.

Recommendations

From conclusions that become exciting particularity ideas in research and development, especially at the school activities, the author provides recommendctio. including Sustainable Islamic behaviour has become the daily life of the Muslim himself as long as he lives as a Muslim; however, training is needed in daily activities that make it consistent with his Islam. Likewise, the environment allows him to be resilient with Islam and able to take advantage of his time to become the best Muslim and strengthen the ummah. The dynamics in students' lives make it dynamic in learning and teaching in the classroom; this is coupled with cultural renewal in several different places that make students able to adapt and make their lives resilient with sustainable Islamic behaviour.

In looking at this Muslim youth problem and the objectives of this topic, the author is influential in guiding me to become a character teacher with solid goals in characterising Muslim students and making their abilities sustainable in cultivating plans to become Muslim students successful. Likewise, the different pedagogy styles, historical foundations, philosophy, and sociology of education, as well as the impact of education on Islamic society and society's impact on education. It has had a significant impact on my teaching philosophy. The Islamic behaviour topic which has affected me most during this thesis: Islamic philosophical foundations of education. These topics will help teachers and all stakeholders to be more open-minded about my teaching practice through the sustainability of Islamic behaviour.

Meanwhile, the objective of this topic is for students to examine various Islamic educational philosophies, their impact on classroom practice, and how academic theory can be applied to classroom practice and instruction models. The Islamic educational Philo was in line with the philosophy of progressivism which focuses on positive changes and problem-solving approaches that people with various academic credentials can provide their students. As a student and teacher, familiarity with the traditional teaching approach is one centre where the teacher is the education centre. That is an approach where the teacher is the only person with Islamic knowledge and tries to impart what he knows to the student and a method where the students have no say. Its been realised that for proper

teaching and learning, the teacher must apply an Islamic student-centred approach where the teacher is just a facilitator of the educational process.

Furthermore, an Islamic student-centred approach to the educational process gives students the freedom to develop naturally through sustainability in Islamic behaviour. It values the scientific method of Islamic teaching, gives freedom to students to have their Islamic boundaries and promotes interaction among students as valuable to the learning process. It also supports the progressivism philosophy, which says the classroom environment must be rich and welcoming for students to be self-mastery, problem thinkers and problem solvers to benefit society, but in the Islamic domain. Providing a rich and sound classroom environment with students' interest materials for free use and full opportunity for self-expression through Islamic education is necessary.

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